

Out Of Court Disposals:

An Unrealised Catalyst For Change In The
Battle Against Drugs-related Offending.

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Abstract

This dissertation examines out-of-court-disposals practice in England & Wales in relation to drugs-related offending and harms, particularly ahead of the new Two-Tier Plus Framework proposed by the s.98-121 of the *Police, Crime, Sentencing, and Courts Act 2022* c.32. The paper considers the provenance of ideological crime-control politics visible in the *Misuse of Drugs Act* c.38 and its siphon into policing, causing discriminatory practices still present today. The paper outlines how orthodox retributive and utilitarian approaches to punishment have led to the current courts backlog and prison crisis, thus setting the stage for innovative methods, such as out-of-court-disposals (OOCs), to better address the exegesis of drugs related offending. The paper considers current concern over OOCs application within England and Wales, employing both doctrinal and sociolegal analysis to present as fuller picture as the limited commentary allows. To enable discussion of ‘what works’ the author provides a systematic analysis of jurisdiction-wide out-of-court-disposal pilots, providing evidenced critique for the draft Code of Practice (Ministry of Justice, 2023) on the new Community Cautions and Diversionary Cautions, has been waiting to be administered by the *Police, Crime, Sentencing, and Courts Act* for some time. The new framework has the potential for a fresh start in evidence-gathering assisting further innovation in this area of criminal justice.

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Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This dissertation evaluates the current out-of-court disposal (OCCD) framework in England and Wales (E&W) in relation to reducing drugs-related offending and harms. It traces the international politics (Jennings *et al.*, 2015) and law as a harbinger of domestic restrictions on substances through the Misuse of Drugs Act 1971 (MDA), and later Psychoactive Substances Act 2016, c.2 (PSA). It will outline current retributivist techniques employed within the criminal justice system (CJS) and their impacts on marginalised (Shiner *et al.*, 2018; Lammy MP, 2017) and drug-using communities (Stevens, 2019). These explorations will form the basis of the argument that prosecution of drug-related culminating is not inherently not in the public interest. (Crown Prosecution Service, 2018)

Pragmatic, evidence-based, diversion (Stevens *et al.*, 2022; Transform Justice, 2022) better addresses the causes of lower-level offending (Collins, Lonczak and Clifasefi, 2019; Neyroud, 2017), *per contra*, its application in E&W has been inconsistent (Shaw, 2022; Mason, 2020), opaque (House of Commons: Justice Committee, 2009) and hesitant to reform (Glen, 2018). The Policing, Crime, Sentencing, and Courts Act (c.32, ss.98-121 (PCSCA)) is poised to 'simplify' (Home Office, 2023b) the OOCDD framework yet overlooks previous recommendations (Slade, 2023). In lieu of a philosophy shift toward decriminalisation, or a health-centred Parliamentary approach (Health and Social Care Committee, 2019; Millar, Jones and Roxburgh, 2008), OOCDDs are an opportunity for the criminal justice system (CJS) to progress and better addresses the characteristics of this *sui generis* form of criminality (Pearson, 1992a). Nevertheless, analysis is needed to ensure the PCSCA does not repeat mistakes of augmenting drug harms and punitive, iatrogenic criminal justice responses (Slade, 2023; Ely, Kew and Jolaoso, 2022).

1.2 Aims & Objectives

Do OOCDDs prove more effective in reducing drugs-related offending and harms than traditional prosecutory measures?

- To examine the origins and efficacy of current criminal justice approaches to reduce drugs-related offending and harms.
- To analyse the benefits and limitations of OOCDDs, particularly in relation to illicit drug use.

- To review the changes to the OOC structure proposed by s.98-121 PCSCA and evaluate its ability to decrease drug-related harms and reoffending.

1.3 Dissertation Structure

Chapter 1 traces the international politics (Haiven, 2018; Pearson, 1992b) and law (UN Convention on Psychotropic Substances 1971, UN Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs 1961) which initiated domestic restrictions within the arbitrary MDA (Nutt, 2020; Rolles and Measham, 2011), as supplemented by the PSA. Ch.1 outlines penal Parliamentary philosophies (Stevens, 2019; The Howard League for Penal Reform, 2017; Shiner and Winstock, 2015) and their half-century stagnation (Home Office, 2023b; Townsend, 2021), evidencing that retributive measures are insufficient, even iatrogenic, at reducing drug use and drugs-related harms (Wakeling and Lynch, 2020; Chamberlain *et al.*, 2019; Babor, 2009). Socio-legal examination of the nuances of drugs-related offending (Beyer, Crofts and Reid, 2002) and drug-using populations (Ouimette and Read, 2014) will demonstrate that inhibition of evidence-led policy has exacerbated user vulnerabilities and volatile police-public relations (Spicer, 2021; Spicer, Moyle and Coomber, 2020; Lammy MP, 2017), and highlight these concerns as present at the MDA's inception. It concludes on retributive approaches' failure to reduce problematic or recreational use (Dame Carol Black, 2020), and facilitation of drug harms by repudiating health and social needs (Kincova and Rolles, 2022; Inderdepartmental Committee on Drug Addiction, 1965). *Ergo*, chapter 1 will carry the body of the core doctrinal analysis, where systematic exposition of rules, norms, and guidelines constitute the dissertation's underpinnings. This situates provisions within the broader 'net' of E&W legal-order (van Gestel and Micklitz, 2011), producing a historical-to-contemporary picture of CJS responses to illicit drug use.

Chapter 2 utilises the Crown Prosecution Service (CPS) and Ministry of Justice (MoJ) guidance/ analysis for the current six-tier OOC framework employed in E&W (Heydari, 2023; Ministry of Justice, 2013, 2014, 2015), which is currently comprised of simple cautions, conditional cautions, penalty notices for disorder, cannabis and khat warnings, and community resolutions. This background will form the basis of sociolegal analysis of their application and procedure in E&W, delineating the 'postcode lottery' of their use (Home Affairs Committee, 2015, p.8), concerns of net-widening (Ofori, 2022; Cohen, 1985, pp.52–53) and mechanisms which worsen racial disparities already entrenched in the CJS (Lammy MP, 2017; Neyroud and Slothower, 2015). Further highlighting how evidence-led practice outlined by the Runciman report and Dame Black's review- two decades later- is still second to ideological politics and legislation (Dame Carol Black, 2020; Viscountess Runciman, 2000).

Chapter 3 situates prior discussion within drugs-related offending, incorporating a systematic review to demonstrate varied approaches to combat its nuances, with the ultimate assessment of reoffending rates (see Appendix A). Studies were gleaned from the Centre for Justice Innovations' 'Mapping Innovation tool' (using search term 'drug', and the focus 'diversion') with forward citation checks to identify programmes no-longer running, resulting in eight suitable schemes (Centre for Justice Innovation, n.d.). The review will provide a backdrop for evaluation of the simplified two-tier OOC framework proposed by s.98-121 PCSCA 2023, including analysis of its draft code of practice (Ministry of Justice, 2023), concluding that the statute is a missed opportunity to realise governmental (Dame Carol Black, 2020; Ames *et al.*, 2018; Home Office, 2013), academic (Lindquist-Grantz *et al.*, 2021; Neyroud, 2017), and independent recommendations (Slade, 2023; Revolving Doors Agency, 2021).

1.4 Conclusion

The conclusion finds that OOCs are more effective in reducing drugs-related offending than traditional prosecutory measures, and proposes recommendations for the PCSCA TTPF's Code of Practice to address the current pitfalls in OOC practice in E&W. It suggests that the TTPF could be a new start, and a comprehensive and clear Code of Practice could hold the potential to harness OOCs potential and improve CJS experience for both drugs users and marginalised communities.

Chapter 2: Drugs Prohibition- An Iatrogenic Prescription

2.1 Introduction

2023 saw the highest annual drug poisoning deaths since records began (5,448), with a minimum of 66.4% of drug-related deaths attributed to “drug misuse” (dependency or abuse of prohibited substances under s.5 MDA (Population Health Monitoring Group, 2024)), doubling since records began in 1993 (2,178, (Handley, Ramsey and Flanagan, 2018)). In 1935 estimations of addict numbers were not beyond 2,000 (Friends of the National Archives, 2020), in comparison to the 777,000 frequent users of illicit substance in E&W today (Office for National Statistics, 2023); changes of, *inter alia*, population size, culture, availability and range of substances, cannot solely explain this increase.

Thus, Chapter 1 explores the provenance of international law which first regulated substance use (International Opium Convention, League of Nations, Treaty Series, vo.8, p.187; United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2008) before it’s ‘criminal label’ was applied by UN Conventions, the backdrop to the substance-use ‘wave’ which has increased exponentially since (the first wave really began in the 1960s (Sparrow, 2014)). It will examine the role of global politics in encouraging the ‘moral sidestep’ of Parliament in disregarding ‘evidence-led’ policy aimed at minimising harms (Stevens, 2019, p.437; pioneered by Russell Newcombe, 1987), in preference for crime control’s ‘tough, escalatory frameworks’ (Home Office, 2022). The chapter will conclude on how current sentences are insufficient, even iatrogenic, at reducing drug use and drugs-related harms (Ministry of Justice, 2024d; Colman and Vander Laenen, 2012).

2.2 The Purpose of Punishment

The purpose of sentencing saw its inaugural definition in s.142 Criminal Justice Act 2003 c.44 (CJA, also see explanatory notes, para 6) as punishment, crime reduction, reform and rehabilitation, public protection and reparation (since repealed- s.416(1), sch.28 Sentencing Act 2020 c.17). To ‘keep people safe’ has been outlined as the primary purpose (Ministry of Justice, 2020), actioned by reducing crime, and thus victimisation, and by punishing law-breakers ‘in a meaningful and proportionate way’ supporting offenders to ‘turn away’ from criminality (Ministry of Justice, 2019). These cogs are difficult to reconcile; to understand the logic of prohibition and its concurrent penal sanctions, theories of punishment must be examined. Since 1971, use of drugs within sch.2 MDA has constituted a punishable

act under *nulla poena sine lege*; duly the aims of punishment must be applied to drugs-related offending.

Prescription of punishment to an undesirable (illegal) act is grounded in the orthodox philosophies of retribution and utilitarianism. They create authorised (Walker, 1991), perhaps paternal (For debate- Ruggiero, 1999; cf Zaibert, 2006), penalties based on deontological or consequentialist justifications. Retribution derives justification through retrospective judgment on criminal transgressions of a rational agent; they are deserving of a prescription of punishment but only in proportion to the offence (Parfit, 2011; Von Hirsch and Ashworth, 2005). This symbolic value creates a moral duty to punish (*jus talionis*- an eye for an eye) to avoid becoming a participant to the crime (bloodguilt (Thomason, 2021)). Some academics alleged retributivism is of 'marginal importance' to CJS in recent decades (Shiner, 2006, p.62), but proportionality is still a central vein of modern criminal justice, exemplified within crime control's contemporary 'war zone' of drug policy (Pearson, 1999, p.478; Ministry of Justice, 2019).

In contrast, utilitarianism, rooted in Marxist criminology, conceptualises crime as a social and political phenomenon (Allen, 1973). It considers that retributivism's 'ethic of individualism' places too great a burden on autonomy, diverting notice from the environmental structures which influence their production (Hagan, 1994). Utilitarianism theories tend towards 'less rather than more' CJS interventions (Braithwaite and Pettit, 1990), suiting the return of laissez-faire politics in the 1980s (Pugh, 2017, p.366). It justifies punishment through harm prevention, whether by general deterrence,¹ incapacity, or rehabilitation in the pursuance of reducing reoffending (Lacey, 1988; Shiner, 2006, p.63): sentences are proportionate to future effects, not the act itself. Legislation violating the 'principle of efficiency' is illegitimate under preventionist justifications and 'should be repealed or modified' to conform with preventionist objectives (Lacey, 1988, pp.118–119). Ashworth, amongst others, forwards that preventionist philosophies are the sole rationale appropriate for modern governance to pursue (von Hirsch and Ashworth, 2005, p.87).

Preventionist justifications employ censure in a 'complementary' capacity (von Hirsch and Ashworth, 2005, p.13; Feinberg, 1970, p.103). The hybrid theory of expressivism uses communicative and communitarian approaches to 'teach a moral lesson' (Ewing, 1929, p.116; Duff, 2001; Braithwaite, 1989) on behalf of symbolic (censure (Sumner, 1990)) and emotional (public (Zimring, 1996)) expressions of undesirable acts. Punishment is legitimised as the vessel for public denunciation; hence it carries the retributive element of proportionality. Expressivism has long been employed to police drug-using populations (For instance- Wall and Grannell, 2023) and their contemporary stigmatisation is entangled, wrongly or rightly (Hadjimatheou, 2016), with the addition of criminal labels (inter alia-

Bernburg, Krohn and Rivera, 2006; Downs, Robertson and Harrison, 1997). Stigmatisation reduces the likelihood of treatment engagement and recovery, a positive factor in desistance from crime (Health and Social Care Committee, 2019, para.59; Colman and Vander Laenen, 2012). Moreover, labelling politically demonises populations through inaccurate ties to drug use, such as those suffering from mental health illnesses (Corrigan, Kuwabara and O’Shaughnessy, 2009) or Black, Asian or minority ethnic groups (BAME) (Hickman, 2000). This disproves the notion that penal labelling abides *nulla poena sine lege* (Stanton-Ife, 2007); denunciation is not reserved for the *de jure* guilty; the presumption of innocence is sidestepped under justifications of individual deterrence. This failure of proof to a ‘requisite level’ (Campbell, 2013, p.690) accentuates that censure should remain a ‘collateral consequence’ of punishment, rather than its engine (Hadjimatheou, 2016, p.570). Although, its moral component forwards restorative processes incorporated into some OOCs (see community resolutions at section 3.3.1 and conditional cautions at 3.3.4), and benefit both the offender and victim(s) (Banjoko, 2009).

2.3 The Provenance of Drugs Prohibition

E&W has not always sat on its ‘high horse of oppression and prohibition’ (Helen Clark, former New Zealand prime minister and chair of the Global Commission on Drug Policy, speaking to Townsend, 2021). The Hague Convention of 1912, with conscription required by the treaty of Versailles (Art 295, Treaty of Peace between the Allied and Associated Powers and Germany (Treaty of Versailles), signed 28th June 1919), limited narcotic manufacture to ‘medical and legitimate purposes’ (*ibid*), including penal sanctions for possession (Art.20, International Opium Convention 1912 (adopted 23 January 1912)). This was ratified through Dangerous Drugs Act 1920 c.46, forsaking the ‘disease concept of addiction’ (Spear, 2002), and restricting the export, import, sale, and distribution of *inter alia*, opium, cocaine, and morphine, through a system of ‘legalised purveying’ (Dr EW Adams, secretary of the Rolleston Committee, quoted in Lindesmith, 1965). This was termed the ‘British System’ and held a ‘liberal reputation’ for its compassionate approach to drug use and addiction (Strang and Gossop, 2005; Berridge, 1980, p.1; Witton, Keaney and Strang, 2005).

2.3.1 The Downfall of the British System

The British System maintained an addict population of under 1000 until the late 1950s (Pierce, 1969) when heroin ‘mini-epidemic’ startled authorities (Pearson, 2001). Despite this population being ‘very small’, evidence that doctor malpractice was ‘attract[ing] new recruits to the rank of addicts’ (Inderdepartmental Committee on Drug Addiction, 1965, paras11, 24, 25 and 50), fuelled notions that tolerant attitudes were responsible (DuPont and Greene, 1973). Conversely, the ‘prohibitionist fervour’

in the USA had seen growing since the 1940s, with drug policy a tool for anti-migration rhetoric (Fisher, 2022; Hari, 2019; Taylor, 2008), a racist ideology which was soon imported to Britain (Kinsella, 2022). Moral panics centred on Cannabis (Klein, 2016), LSD (Oakley, 2012), and 'pep-pills' (amphetamine) use amongst teenagers, (Teff, 1972) citing 'social acceptance' (Interdepartmental Committee on Drug Addiction, 1965, para.40), today's 'normalisation' (Parker, Aldridge and Measham, 1998) as the pathway to heroin addiction (Interdepartmental Committee on Drug Addiction, 1965, para.40). The gateway of 'soft' to 'hard' drugs proved persuasive in tightening drugs legislation (Sub-Committee of the CID Committee of the Association of Chief Police Officers, 1970).

Within international arenas, the UN codified the existing treaty law under the 1961 Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs, limiting use to medical and scientific purposes under Art 4(c). This was followed by the Drugs Act of 1964 (Drugs (Prevention of Misuse) Act c.64 (DPMA)) and 1965 (Dangerous Drugs Act c.15), creating an unauthorised possession offence to tackle panic of contamination (s.1 DPMA (Bewley, 1965)); inaugural expressivist punishment saw users dehumanised as a vector of disease. Despite difficulty in distinguishing between 'clients' and 'pushers' (Advisory Committee on Drug Dependence and Wayne, 1970), further police powers of arrest were ushered in the Dangerous Drugs Act of 1967 (c.82), resulting in a 28% rise in drug convictions between 1967-1968 (HL Deb 14 January 1971, Vol 314, Col 223). The Wootton inquiry concluded that drug sentences were too severe (Advisory Committee on Drug Dependence, 1968, pp.7, 13, 15, 20–21); these are tempered in comparison to today's (Possession of a Class A substance can incur life imprisonment under s.1 Controlled Drugs (Penalties) Act 1958 c.39, see Sentencing Council, 2021b). The Wootton reports recommendations angered anti-reformist Home Secretary, James Callaghan, who, amongst the political climate of Nixon's War on Drugs, was embracing the international prohibitionist stance (HC Deb, 23 January 1969, Vol 776, Cols 661–3; Mitchell, 1969; Oakley, 2012). It appeared that evidence-led responses were inferior to the appearance of parliamentary supremacy (HC Deb, 27 January 1969, Vol 776, Col 949); Callaghan tabled his Misuse of Drugs Bill in March 1970 (HC Deb, 25 March 1970, Vol 79,8 Cols 1447-8). The President of the Public Health Inspectors Association drew attention to 'small amount of effective and valuable research' on the topic on which they were legislating, and instead outlines that a multi-agency response of health, counselling, and education would be most effective- 'whatever penal provisions we make... they do not provide a cure' (Blenkinsop MP, *ibid*, cols 1471-1474). Fortunately, Callaghan's bill was dropped before it could reach the House of Lords but saw reintroduction later that year by the Conservatives (HC Deb, 16 July 1970, Vol 803, Cols 1749-802). In May 1971, the MDA's 'new machinery of control' replaced the 'fragmented' drugs legislation of E&W (HL Deb 14 January 1971, Vol 314, Col 225 & 230), and the British System drew its final breath.

2.4 The Misuse of Drugs Act 1971

The UN's 1961 Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs was anomalous in its effort to 'protect people against themselves' with 'such zeal' (Pearson, 1999). Prior to the MDA, Britain's approach to drugs policy was 'dictated by international commitments' (Teff, 1972, p.288). MacGregor argues the MDA created a dichotomous partnership of 'care' (the 'disease'-concept of addiction under the British System (South, 2002) and 'control' responses, as personified in modern CJS practices (MacGregor, 1999, p.82). She advances that these regime typologies represent pragmatism on one hand, and 'moralistic or ideological' policy on the other (*ibid*).

'The wider responsibility which we all have... [to] those involved in social and health problems... the less disappointment we shall have about the future' Blenkinsop MP (HC Deb, 25 March 1970, Vol 798, Cols 1471-2).

'If the house had known then what we know now, passing the Act would have been an appalling betrayal of its duty to the public interest.' Crispin Blunt MP, (HC Deb 17 June 2021, Vol 697, Col 500).

These quotes, fifty years apart, illustrate that E&W's fundamental instrument for drug control - the MDA (Viscountess Runciman, 2000, p.11) - did not foster societal 'health and welfare' as international prohibition pressures intended (Preamble, UN Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs). The failure of penal prohibition is visible; in 2018, the UN recommended that all member states 'promote alternatives to conviction and punishment in appropriate cases, including the decriminalisation of possession for personal use' (United Nations Chief Executives Board for Coordination, 2019).

2.4.1 Drug Classification under the MDA

S.2 of the MDA introduced a three-tier classification system of A-C (contained in Sch.2), purportedly based on a substances 'evidence of harm', prevalence, and associated illegal activity (Explanatory Memorandum to the Misuse of Drugs Act 1971 (Amendment) Order 2024' CO/EM/2022.3. paras 2.1 and 6.1), accompanied by escalating sentences (s 25 and Sch 4 MDA). This shrine to actuarial criminology (See Feeley and Simon, 1992) was absent in its calibration to scientific understandings of risk, harm, and addictiveness; no explicit criteria was used in the strata's development (Viscountess Runciman, 2000). In the half-century since, several inquiries (House of Commons: Science and Technology Committee, 2006; Viscountess Runciman, 2000) and expert commentary have designated the MDA's classifications as 'not fit for purpose' (Shiner, 2015; Nutt *et al.*, 2007). This demonstrates

that the ‘politically charged atmosphere’ of legislating a phenomena not ‘easily amenable’ to regulation has created ‘tension between and evidence and values’ (Monaghan, 2014, p.1026; Teff, 1972, p.225; MacGregor, 2013, p.227),

This is keenly demonstrated by the ‘debacle’ of cannabis reclassification in the noughties (Shiner, 2015; Turnbull, 2009, p.202; May *et al.*, 2002, p.202). The MDA-created Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs (ACMD) recommended reclassification to class C at the turn of the century (Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs, 2002; HC Home Affairs Committee, 2002; Viscountess Runciman, 2000, para.28), which New Labour obliged in 2004 (The Misuse of Drugs Act 1971 (Modification) (No. 2) Order, SI No.2003/3201; HC Deb 10 February 2004, Vol 417, Cols 315-358). The opposition alleged this labelled cannabis ‘safe’ to potential users, with New Labour hinting to a U-turn preceding the 2005 general election (Oliver, 2005). The Secretary of State instigated a report which recommended cannabis’ continued class C categorisation and a health-based response to use (Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs, 2008, p.39). In 2009, this evidence-based expertise, was disregarded when cannabis was reinstated it as a Class B (The Misuse of Drugs Act 1971 (Amendment) Order, SI No.2008/3138) and flanked by increased penalties (Turnbull, 2009, p.205). This highlights that the exegesis of policy decisions lies in ‘political rhetoric and appearance’ (Garland, 2002, p.111), not objective assessment of social problems as stated by S 1(2) MDA.

2.4.2 The Psychoactive Substances Act 2016

The ill-founded global strategy of classification was ‘floundering’ under the dynamic emergence of ‘legal highs’ from the mid-2000s (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2013). These ‘novel psychoactive substances’ (NPS) mimicked the effects of drugs subject to control under the MDA (Humphries, 2022). Once a NPS was prohibited within Sch.2 MDA, supplier ‘head shops’ would alter the chemical structure to abscond from its MDA definition, therefore making the substance licit and able to be openly sold (Deen *et al.*, 2021; Kelly, 2011). The appeal of these substances was attributed to, *inter alia*, their legal status, immunity from drugs tests, and dangerous false beliefs they may be safer than illicit drugs (Mathews *et al.*, 2019; Brunt *et al.*, 2017; Bonar, Ashrafioun and Ilgen, 2014; Fantegrossi *et al.*, 2014), all a direct consequence of the government’s oversight in the MDA’s classification system. Temporary Class Drug Orders were made from 2011 in an attempt to curtail use (Sch.17 under s.151, Police Reform and Social Responsibility Act 2011 c.13), but still required preliminary evidence harms in the ‘lengthy process’ of legislative amendments (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2013, p.31; Home Office, 2011). The PSA ended this game of ‘cat and mouse’ (Newton, 2016) by introducing a blanket

ban on any substance capable of ‘producing a psychoactive effect’, *inter alia*, emotions and the nervous system (S.2.1(a) and S.2(2) PSA).

The Act was rushed (Home Affairs Committee, Psychoactive Substances (HC 2015-16, 361)); the ACMD were not consulted during the bill’s development, contravening legal obligations. Moreover, lessons from Ireland’s blanket ban in 2010 were ignored, leading to criminalisation of younger populations (Release, Transform Drug Policy Foundation, 2015; European Commission, 2014), therefore increasing the likelihood of future drug addiction. The PSA is testimony that political rhetoric, rather than evidence, is the provenance of drug policymaking, to deadly consequences. Whilst deaths involving NPS went down following the PSA, pre-warned displacement occurred, where users returned to ‘traditional’ drugs at doses they could no longer tolerate following the PSA coming into force and drug deaths increased the following year (Deen *et al.*, 2021). Production and distribution of NPSs were pushed underground, reducing opportunities for education and harm reduction, and exposing users to the darknet and organised crime (Deligianni *et al.*, 2020). This was an acceptable cost for the executive as health-based measures would have exposed the MDA’s absurdity (Release, Transform Drug Policy Foundation, 2015). The PSA’s only progression was an absence of criminalisation for simple possession. *Per contra*, this is unsurprising, as the definition of NPS was so wide as to feasibly include perfume or eye drops (Dunt, 2015). The PSA thus confirms the legislatures conviction to the outdated principles of the MDA.

2.5 Drug use in E&W

2.5.1 The Causes of Drug Use

To understand policy responses, the prevalence of drug use must be examined. Use of illicit substances by the general population has increased 24% since the 1960s, with 3.1% of the population currently exhibiting symptoms of dependence (McManus *et al.*, 2014, p.266; Benedictus, 2011). Drug harms are felt disproportionately across society, key predictors of addiction include poverty, particularly homelessness (Manhica *et al.*, 2021; Dietz, 2009), social exclusion (Manhica *et al.*, 2021; Buchanan, 2004), and unemployment (Nagelhout *et al.*, 2017). The epidemiology of use tends towards the cognitively immature, seeing decreasing use once individuals enter their 20s (Office for National Statistics, 2023; Aldridge, Measham, and Williams, 2011; Steinberg, 2008). Familial drug use a predictor; dependence is 40-60% genetic (Button *et al.*, 2006). Experience of adverse life events, trauma, and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (Bailey and Stewart, 2014; Felitti, 2003), particularly in childhood (Zarse *et al.*, 2019), can cause neurotoxic effects, which impact behaviour regulation (Sullivan, 2017)

and increased likelihood of physical and mental disorders, including drug addiction (Ayres, 2021; Zarse *et al.*, 2019; Felitti, 1993). Trauma at a young age increases chances of developing Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, which, at minimum, doubles the likelihood of use (Karlstad *et al.*, 2016). Unsurprisingly, co-morbidity is common, 51.2% of adults exhibiting signs of drug dependency current receive mental health treatment (NHS Digital, National Centre for Social Research, 2021). Scientific developments have established it is not trauma *per se* but avoidance coping strategies which are associated with drug (particularly problematic) use (Ayres, 2021; Wong *et al.*, 2013). Victims of psychosocial stress from marginalised groups are thus further disadvantaged by being unable to access mental health care (Lowther-Payne *et al.*, 2023). Not only can illicit drug use be an inevitable result of childhood adversity but is symptomatic of wider social injustice. This evidence rejects censure of addicts as ‘self-centred lost souls’ (Home Sec Callaghan, ‘HC Deb, 25 March 1970, Vol 798, Cols 1446-1450), thus questioning the ‘*just deserts*’ nature of those punished under the MDA (see section 2.2).

2.5.2 The Drugs/Crime Nexus

Drug offences recorded by the police equal >0.1% individuals who report use in E&W (0.62%, on comparison of the 3.1million reported users in the CSEW, with 50,000 recorded drug offences 2018/19, see Ministry of Justice, 2024b; Allen and Tunnicliffe, 2021). This dark figure renders the drugs/crime nexus obtuse, and yet to be ‘fully delineated’ (Hayhurst *et al.*, 2019, p.114; Bennett, Holloway and Farrington, 2008). Heroin was estimated to generate 40% of acquisitive (‘income-generating’) crime in E&W prior to the millennium, a pattern observed in modern drug diversion studies (Viggiani, 2022, p.32; Home Office, 2016, p.2; Hough, 1996, p.19; Gandossy *et al.*, 1980, p.52). Causal factors for addiction and criminality often overlap; drugs-related offending is tied to recidivism and drug use (Niemelä *et al.*, 2008). This has led to many ‘common cause’ theories (For example Gottfredson and Hirschi, 1990; White and Gorman, 2000), as causation of drugs to crime, or vice versa, is difficult to establish (Bennett, Holloway and Farrington, 2008). Meta analyses on links between non-financial crimes and drug use are also inconclusive (Chaiken and Chaiken, 1990). Since drug use is within the realm of CJSs, not public health, its underlying causes are considerably more difficult to detangle, particularly as interaction with the CJS is a causal factor in and of itself (Winkelman, Chang and Binswanger, 2018).

2.6 Policing of Drug Offences

2.6.1 Crime Control and Drugs Policing

Police involvement with illicit substance use increased during the 1960s (see section 2.3.1, also South, 2002; Spear, 2002) and was extended by s.23 MDA to include, *inter alia*, S&S on 'reasonable grounds'. The mid-1970s neoliberal philosophies, realised in Thatcher's 'law and order' penal politics, fostered police who were 'more explicitly politically active than at any other time' (Henry and Smith, 2007, p.9). BAME communities, already subject to overt police racism and without protection (Whitfield, 2004; Layton-Henry, 1984), were victims of police discriminately exercising historic 'sus' laws (s.4 Vagrancy Act 1824 c.83) and MDA's S&S under the guise of 'justice' (Farrall, Burke and Hay, 2016). Examples include 'Operation Swamp' (named after Thatcher's anti-migration rhetoric (Gordon Burns interviewing Thatcher, 1978)) where S&S was used to harass young black populations, culminating in the 'race riots' which spanned several English cities in 1980/1 (Rollo, 1980, p.193). The following Scarman inquiry concluded this was an outburst of 'resentment by young black people against the police', 'almost akin to a civil war' (Fryer, 1984, p.392; Lord Scarman OBE, 1981). Due to this black activism, the 'sus' low threshold was repealed later that year (S.10, see schedule on part II repeals, Criminal Attempts Act 1981 c.47).

This reprieve was short-lived. In 1984 the Police and Criminal Evidence Act c.60 (PACE) significantly increased police powers, including S&S under s.1 (the provision used for 99% of recorded S&S today (Home Office, 2024, tbl.SS_01)). *Per contra*, it did formalise powers when police use of 'trickery' was normalised (McNee, 1983, p.18), in a wider society which was learning to not 'accept [this] fiction of consent' (Dixon, 2008, p.24). PACE was seen as an embodiment of the 'Thatcherite programme' authoritarian populism endorsing experimental forms of crime control and threatening civil liberties (Scruton, 1987, p.viii; Jennings *et al.*, 2015; Peplow, 2019). This emergence of 'hard policing' followed the Regan's 1982 'Just Say No' campaign, recommitting the USA, and thus the international community, to Nixon's war on drugs. Domestically, life imprisonment for drug offences was introduced (S.1, Controlled Drugs (Penalties) Act 1958 c.39).

This punitivism did not reduce harms. The New Right's deindustrialisation of the North caused severe socioeconomic disparities (Millar *et al.*, 2006) resulting in a heroin epidemic seeing 10,000 user deaths in 1987 (Morgan, 2014; De Angelis, Hickman and Yang, 2004). Press-induced moral panics linked illicit substances to new subcultures (e.g., 'acid house' (Hill, 2002)), who rejected the hegemony of 'great moral politics' under Thatcher (Young, 1993, p.353). Despite the Met Commander's acknowledgement

that current approaches were failing, the deluge of ‘penal populism’ continued (Garland, 2002; Grieve, 1993). With a predilection to retribution weakly related to crime rate (Zimring and Johnson, 2006), voter hysteria grew, peaking in E&W in 1992 (Jennings *et al.*, 2015, fig.2). This culminated in further ill-founded legislation of the Criminal Justice and Public Order Act 1994 c.33, driving drugs policy firmly into the domain of ideological condemnation, not evidenced-based reason.

2.6.2 The Risk Society – Actuarial Criminology

A further theory of punishment omitted from section 2.2 is the New Penology (also known as actuarial criminology), which was first identified in 1992 (Feeley and Simon, 1992). The 1980’s ‘crisis of penal modernism’ (Garland, 2002; Meranze, 1998) saw ‘risk-profiling’ (Giddens, 1991) attempt to convert the uncertainties of late modernity’s contemporary and economic changes into tangible categories able to be mitigated (Garland, 2002; Cohen, 1985). Like expressivism, actuarial approaches do not require criminality for authoritarian interference. Instead, statistical assessment of stratified risk aggregates (Floud, 1982), *inter alia* problematic substance use, childhood trauma, and parental drug use (for example, see HM Prison & Probation Service, 2023), are denoted criminogenic factors to form predictive judgements on the ‘actuarial man’ (Garland, 2002). Therefore, individuals from adverse circumstances are not only more likely to have increased likelihood of criminal justice involvement due to their undesirability within the status quo (see sections 2.5.1, 2.6.3, and 2.6.4), but actuarial policing sees increased satisfaction of risk thresholds which justify police, rather than social service, involvement. For example, working-class identity is not a predictor of drug abstinence or use (Eastwood, 2019), but working-class users are more likely to face criminal justice consequences under the MDA (Shiner *et al.*, 2018).

2.6.3 Public Spaces in the Policing of Drugs Offences

Unequal CJS representation of certain aggregates can also be attributed to visibility; vulnerable substance users are more likely to be care experienced (Maliszewski and Brown, 2014), meaning they will have a portfolio of misbehaviour and risk-factors ready for assessment by criminal justice agencies (Lindquist and Santavirta, 2014). Furthermore, drug users are more likely to be young, or homeless, *ergo* visible in public spaces. They are targets of situational crime prevention (College of Policing, 2022), more likely to be selected for a S&S (52% of searches are carried out on those between 10–24-year-olds, Home Office, 2024), or unable to conduct publicly undesirable acts in private (Pable, 2012). As the executive director of non-profit *Release* stated, ‘drugs are decriminalised in the UK- if you are a white privileged MP’ (Eastwood, 2019); only users who are visible are likely to be met with the stunted arm of the law. Whilst the causal factors for drug use may contribute to lower-income bands having higher

rates of substance use (see section 2.5.1), Class As are used most by those earning over £52,000 per year (Office for National Statistics, 2023). *Per contra*, those from disadvantaged groups, including victims of crime and those living in socially rented accommodation, are more likely to be stopped (Bradford, 2016, p.123). The CJS may be conceptualised as a mechanism for suppression of the ‘relatively economic poor’ (Dollar, 2019, p.305), as they are considered economically and politically threatening to hegemonic power (Kraus *et al.*, 2011; Wright, 2009). This aggregate has grown considerably in recent years amongst the financial crash, covid-19, and austerity (Francis-Devine, 2024), *ergo*, increasing potential hostility under this theory (Zweig, 2000).

2.6.4 Police Powers, Prejudice & Discretion

Whilst S&S can be an ‘important means of detecting offenders’ (Viscountess Runciman, 2000, p.90), it is more effective when used sparingly; in 2023, 70.7% resulted in NFA (Home Office, 2024, tbl.2.2). Weak grounds undermine the legitimacy of S&S (Independent Office for Police Conduct, 2022, p.14) and are particularly present within the ‘impossible mandate’ of drugs policing (Manning, 1997); black men are eight times more likely to be searched than whites, yet are half as likely to use substances (Office for National Statistics, 2023, tbl.3.01). Three decades after the race riots, the Metropolitan police were found to be institutionally racist (Sir William Macpherson, 1999, para.6.48), which further prevails today (Casey, 2023). These prejudices mark the ‘start’ of a black individuals criminal justice journey (Lammy MP, 2017), unjustly destabilising individuals, families, and having a ‘corrosive-effect’ on communities (in correspondance to points: Kruttschnitt and Husserman, 2008; The Howard League for Penal Reform, 2011; Young Review/Black Training and Enterprise Group (BTEG) June 2016, quoted in Lammy MP, 2017, p.17). Moreover, it fundamentally usurps the aims of CJSs, as over-policing prompts defiance (Hough, 2013; Sherman, 1993), evidenced in the plethora of protests marking this last decade (*inter alia*, Palestine Action, Kill the Bill, Extinction Rebellion, and Black Lives Matter protests). Nevertheless, little more than lip-service changes to this ‘drugs apartheid’ (Taylor, Buchanan and Ayres, 2016, p.453) have been heralded as sufficient by government agents (Home Affairs Committee, 2021); racism is still fuelling drugs prohibition as it did at its inception.

Policing powers have been regarded as a ‘controlling, disciplinary tool’, aimed at criminals or the socially undesirable (Bradford, 2016, p.123; Harkin, 2015). Police can be political agents (see section 2.6.1), and whilst steps towards evidence-based policing have been taken in the last twenty years, cynics may argue that adaption of new policing technologies under actuarial models act as a scapegoat for racial bias and other prejudice (see section 2.6.2; Ferguson, 2017). These intelligence models are derived from the established basis of ‘best available’ (Klose, 2024) ‘evidence’ in the form of police crime

statistics, so, like other 'AI' models, face issues of emulating, and, amplifying human bias (Tian *et al.*, 2021), perhaps visible in the high-profile S&S of black athletes by Met police in 2020 (Dearden, 2020).

Conversations of police intelligence systems aside, the purpose of S&S is 'nothing if not an attempt to influence the behaviour of the person stopped' (Bradford, 2016, p.47). Researchers must be conscious of 'explaining away' disproportionality, *inter alia*, public space 'availability' of individuals (see section 2.6.3; *ibid* p.69; *cf* Waddington, Stenson and Don, 2004). Intelligence models still operate within the sphere of police discretion, as officers still possess 'choice in any situation', by nature of the breadth of their work (Huff, 2021; Brown, 1988). Beyond role and force culture, Paoline unearthed seven analytically distinct groups of officers, yet their was high levels of consensus of selective enforcement across all categories (Paoline, 2004, p.227). In 1980, Sherman conceptualised police decision-making as falling into five categories: individual (civilian/ officer level characteristics), situational, organisational, community, and legal (Sherman, 1980). The decision to arrest (arguably the most influential in the CJS (Walker, 1993)) can also be divided into two categories: (a) those which are mandated by law and (b) discretionary arrests (Huff, 2021). As most police-civilian contact involves less severe offences with uncertain evidence (Engel *et al.*, 2019), these arrests are more likely to be discretionary, or a result of selective enforcement (Davis, 1969). In drugs policing, this is evidenced by 3% of officers conducting 20% of all arrests. In relation of cannabis warnings; these allow officers 'a great deal of discretion' (Trace, Klein and Roberts, 2004, p.4; May *et al.*, 2002). *Ergo*, discretionary arrest arbiters will face more extraneous factors than mandatory arrests (Huff, 2021). Furthermore, one in five officers are estimated to suffer from PTSD, with many unaware of their conditions (Foley and Massey, 2021; Police Care UK, University of Cambridge, 2019), which has a significant effect on emotional reasoning, and thus can amplify personal bias (Woods, 2016; Verduijn *et al.*, 2015). This further demonstrates that the outcomes of drugs policing are the results of the lottery, with marginalised groups entered in proportions far exceeding their drug use and deserved punishment under retributive justifications.

Returning to the concept of 'best evidence', academics have falsely argued that the overrepresentation of BAME individuals in police statistics is too substantial to be the result of 'mistaken' arrests (Reiner, 2010, p.168). Beyond giving police data an, knowingly, undeserved weight¹ these theories omit consideration of false inaction; incidents where white individuals should have been arrested (Bradford, 2016, p.71). In reality, victim surveys suggest that BAME individuals are significantly less likely to offend

¹ 0.62%, on comparison of the 3.1million reported users in the CSEW, with 50,000 recorded drug offences 2018/19, see 'Criminal Justice Statistics Quarterly, England and Wales, Year Ending June 2023' (n 265); Allen and Tunnicliffe, 2021.

(Sharp and Budd, 2005). Regardless of the provenance of this discrimination (Reiner, 2010, pp.170–171), it is clear that many factors outside of the control of the alleged offender contribute to criminal justice decisions; police arbiters have been coined ‘deserving’ justice (Zane and Mears, 2023). This not only produces disparate outcomes for those already maltreated by society but creates uncertainty, disrupting the utilitarian theory of Rational Choice which civilians purportedly utilise on the path to criminality (section 2.3.1; Paternoster *et al.*, 2015). Thus, proving that our current system within prohibition is not only guilty of perpetrating drug harms, but drug-related criminality.

2.7 The Futility of current penal approaches

2.7.1 The Court’s Backlog

The majority of MDA-created offences were for unlawful possession (s.5(2) & (3), s.9(c), and intent to supply under s.4(3) MDA) rejecting the Wooton report’s recommendations (section 2.3.1), and failing utilitarian justifications (section 2.2) as penal approaches have been acknowledged as ‘unduly blunt instrument’ since the MDA’s inception (HL Deb 14 January 1971, Vol 314, Col, 223; ‘HC Deb 25 March 1970 Vol 798 Col 1471). Deterrent pathways require the police to capture a substantial proportion of people who use drugs, which had proved to be near impossible (Hughes *et al.*, 2019). Viscountess Runciman’s 2000 review recommended that where problem drug use is not apparent, possession alone, even repeated, should not inevitably result in conviction (para.5.11). *Per contra*, drug possession charges amount to 70% of total prosecuted drug offences (Sentencing Council, 2011). Currently, courts in E&W have an unprecedented backlog, with indictable sentences near stationary (Davies, 2023, p.17; Sturge, 2023, p.15; Ungood-Thomas, 2022). Custody time limits (under s.4(1) Bail Act 1976 c.63) have seen debate under international human rights law (McConville and Marsh, 2022), and capacity issues as reasoning for extension should be approached with ‘great caution’ (*R v Manchester Crown Court Ex p McDonald* [1999] 1 WLR 841, p.848).

Utilitarianism requires ‘swift’ justice for effective punishment (Harcourt, 2013, p.1); prolonged periods before an offender must answer for their alleged behaviour prevents censure’s desired effects. As drug offences are charged/summonsed at a rate only second to possession of weapon (Home Office, 2023a, tbl.2.2), increased out-of-court responses to drugs use would have a significant impact to improve deterrent objectives and the court’s backlog. Moreover, multiple court appearances for low-level offending have been found to produce a ‘tariff escalating’ effect (Raynor, 2012, p.934). The same could be said for the ‘net-widening’ nature of OOCs (see section 3.4.3), however they carry justification beyond retributive and utilitarian ideologies.

2.7.2 Prison and Drugs-related Offending

Runciman understood prison to be ‘not commensurate’ with the harm of possession only offences (para.5.12); failing proportionality requirements of retributivism. Yet, custodial sentences are applicable even to summary Class C possession-only offences (s.5(2) MDA); a third of the prison population is connected to drugs-related offending (Dame Carol Black, 2020, para.18). This cohort averages 17.5% of the remand population,² a significant contributor to the- inaccurately termed- prison ‘crisis’ (Johnston and Smith, 2018, p.224); including chronic overcrowding, lack of capacity, rising suicide rates, and concerns of increasing ‘squalor’ (Pina-Sánchez *et al.*, 2023; Ministry of Justice, 2022; HM Prison & Probation Service and Ministry of Justice, 2023; Chief Inspector, 2024). In this event, any proportionality to offence is no longer served, as a prison sentence today is not comparable to a decade prior. Despite this, individual deterrence is still not achieved; drug use is widespread- 15% of prisoners test positive for illicit substances, compared to 9.5% of the general population (Dame Carol Black, 2020, p.27; *cf* Office for National Statistics, 2023). At the MDA’s inception, Callaghan acknowledged that a key benefit of prison was provision for treatment (HC Deb 25 March 1970, Vol 798, Col 1474). *Per contra*, median average custodial sentence lengths do not sit above 1.9 months for possession of a Class A, and rarely reach a month for Class B and C (Sentencing Council, 2021a, tbl.4.3). In this time, addicted prisoners are unlikely to be triaged, let alone see treatment (Dame Carol Black, 2020, para.20). This highlights that utilitarian aims of deterrence and rehabilitation *de facto* see minimal fruition.

On release, ex-prisoners frequently turn to risky alcohol and drug use (Ramsay, 2003; Nurco, Hanlon and Kinlock, 1991). Yet, worryingly, transition to community treatment faces ‘significant problems’; less than a third of drug users receive it within three weeks of release, and for opioid users it is one in ten (Dame Carol Black, 2020, para.23). One in 200 injecting adult males die a fortnight after release (Bird and Hutchinson, 2003), an unjustifiably high price to pay for their offences under any ideal. Inescapably, over half go on to reoffend (58.3% for offences less than 6 months, 55.5% for less than 12 months, Ministry of Justice, 2024d). Drug-use recovery is a positive factor in desistance from crime; 71% of those who take a drug within sch.2 of the MDA month prior to custody go onto reoffend, contrasted with 30% who have never used a substance (Colman and Vander Laenen, 2012; Ministry of Justice, 2011). Hence, assisting offenders to successfully address problematic drug use would benefit preventative philosophies of offending, reduce the ‘risk’ they pose to society, and reduce the current pressures on the prison system.

² 14% of the untried population and 21% of the convicted unsentenced population, ‘Offender Management Statistics Quarterly: July to September 2023’ (Home Office, 2024).

2.8 Conclusion

Through the retributive, utilitarian, expressivist, and actual philosophies of punishment, E&Ws' primary drugs statute, the MDA and PSA, is evidenced as emerging from insecure politics and conjecture, not evidence of harms-reduction or reduction in criminality (Brownlee, 1998). The British system, maintained for much of the 20th century is a long-forgotten era in compassion and scientifically informed process. Imported ideological politics and neoliberalism ensured that the damage of the MDA on vulnerable drug-using communities was further enforced by racist and heavy-handed policing, distancing communities and marring police-public relations to the present day. The current approach's futility has been acknowledged by actors within and outside CJSs, yet contemporary issues such as the courts backlog and prison crisis has not been sufficient to turn the tide on drugs prohibition.

Chapter 3: Out-of-court-disposals In E&W

3.1 Introduction

OOCs have been the subject of police innovation, and debate, frequently in the last decade (Heydari, 2022; Rowley, 2022; HM Government and College of Policing, 2014b; Ministry of Justice and Grayling, 2014); 196,000 issued between June 2022-2023 (Ministry of Justice, 2024b, p.6). They are soon to be altered by the mandatory Two-Tier Plus Framework (TTPF), under s.6 PCSCA, as recommended by the 2020 white paper *A Smarter Approach to Sentencing* (Ministry of Justice, CP 292, pp 37-38, 52-54). They have also undergone a terminology change to 'Out of Court Resolutions' (Heydari, 2023), however, this paper will use the 'Out of Court Disposals' terminology in-line with statute and common understandings. Due to the limited scope of the paper, youth-specific disposals will not be examined.

The primary purpose of OOCs is to 'allow the police to deal quickly and proportionately with low-level' offending when it would be 'disproportionate' to conclude in prosecution (Birtwistle, 2013, p.4), particularly to address 'early stages of offending behaviour' (Ministry of Justice, 2020, p.52). OOCs are a form of diversion, whilst this has no legal definition, it can be conceptualised as preventing prosecution of individuals following an offence (HM Inspectorate of Probation, 2023). Diversion has always existed in the form of informal cautions and NFA, in addition to the recent Outcome 22 which allows for diversionary conditions to be attached to a NFA (Grant, 2022). These mechanisms prevent reoffending, both by preventing prison sentences where individuals may undergo 'criminal education', and by addressing the route of offending behaviour, like substance issues (section 2.5.2; Glen, 2018, p.4). OOC's 'early, rehabilitative, interventions' are mainly final (Ministry of Justice, 2020, pp.73-74). There is a range of OOCs available in a criminal context, this chapter will examine: Community Resolutions (CRs), Cannabis/Khat Warnings (CWs/KWs), Penalty Notices for Disorder (PNDs), Simple Cautions (SCs) and Conditional Cautions (CCs).

There are other examples of non-prosecution measures in E&W. For example, Fixed-Penalty Notices (FPNs) arose as the first OOC in the 1950s (then, s.51-90 Road Traffic Act 1988 c.53) and now cover, *inter alia*, trespassing, littering, truancy, and breach of Covid-19 regulations (in order: s.1-2 Criminal Justice and Police Act 2001 c.16; s.23 Anti-social Behaviour Act 2008 c.38; and e.g., The Health Protection (Coronavirus, Restrictions) (Steps) (England) Regulations 2021 (SI 2020/364) Regulations 12-17).

3.2 Non-prosecution decision-making

The CPS, and police, dictate prosecution arbiters by means the Full Code Test (FCT) (The Crown Prosecution Service, 2020, para.8.4 secs5; Crown Prosecution Service, 2018, secs4–5). Depending on offence severity, the police may be a sole administrator under s.17 of the Criminal Justice and Courts Act 2015 (CJCA c.2). Although, offences viable for CCs have been extended under s.133 of the Legal Aid, Sentencing and Punishment of Offenders Act 2012 (LASPO c.10; in addition to extensions under the CJA). The first FCT stage is satisfied by sufficient evidence for a real prospect of conviction by an ‘objective, impartial, and reasonable jury or bench’, including consideration of any defences (Crown Prosecution Service, 2018, para.4.7). If this is fulfilled, decision continues to the second ‘public interest’ stage. Here, an OOCd may be issued instead of prosecution if deemed an ‘appropriate response to the offender and/or the seriousness and consequences of the offending’ (*ibid*, para.7.1). This will consider the offender’s antecedents (circumstantial and criminal) and the impact of the offence (The Crown Prosecution Service, 2020, para.8.1 and 8.10), including taking note of the victim(s) viewpoints (Ministry of Justice, 2024a, para.6.7). Therefore, OOCds should only be used on *prima facie* satisfaction of the evidential stage, not in instances of ‘contested cases’ (Birtwistle, 2013, p.5). OOCds are not intended for ‘serious’ or ‘persistent’ cases (*ibid*, p.5), *per contra*, there are examples of misapplication which blur the lines on what is prosecution appropriate (Magistrates’ Association, 2022; The Crown Prosecution Service, 2022; Police and Crime Commissioner for Dyfed-Powys, 2021).

3.3 Types of OOCd

3.3.1 Community Resolutions

CRs are non-statutory but are nationally recognised as the lowest policing disposal type (Heydari, 2023). They were trialled in 2008 and introduced nationally in 2009 (West Midlands Police, 2009), they now constitute 71% of OOCds issued (Ministry of Justice, 2024b, p.6). They require guilt, and can be administered by any warranted officer, often when a victim does not wish to pursue formal action (Heydari, 2023, para.2.1, 2.3, and 3.1.1; Marshall, 2012). Consideration of application includes relevant offending history, with a CR likely deemed inappropriate if offences have been committed in the 12 months prior (Heydari, 2023, para.2.1; Marshall, 2012, para.2.2). *Per contra*, training standards have not been mandated beyond ‘appropriate awareness’ of the CR guidelines (Heydari, 2023, para.3.1.4). They frequently incorporate reparation such as restorative justice (RJ), where the victim and offender voluntarily meet to discuss the impact of the offence, under supervision of trained officers or partner services (Heydari, 2023, para.2.4; Marshall, 2012, para.1.1.3; Shewan, 2011). CR conditions can be instantaneous or deferred, but as they are non-statutory, these cannot be legally enforced or escalated

(Heydari, 2023, para.1.7 and 2.4.1). CRs do not incur a criminal record, nor are they stored on the Police National Computer (PCN), but may be used for local intelligence purposes, or arbiters following future offences (West Midlands Police, ND).

3.3.2 Cannabis & Khat Warnings

CWs, a non-statutory OOC, were introduced in 2004 as a ‘preferred’ alternative to arrest in instances of personal possession during the debacle of cannabis reclassification (Hayman, 2003, para.4.1; section 2.4.1). Curiously, CWs are punitive rather than rehabilitative, as they only incur a £90 fine, not drug-specific conditions (GOV.UK, n.d.). CWs sit within an escalatory framework (see fig.1), where aggravating factors, including repeat offending, result in escalating criminal justice measures (Byrne, 2009, sec.2.2). KWs followed khat’s addition to the schedules of the MDA in 2014 (Bliss, 2016; Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs, 2005, 2013), which was controversial and contravened recommendations by the ACMD (Birrell, 2014). A substance mainly consumed by those following cultural practice in East Africa and the Arabian Peninsula, khat is a mild stimulant with minimal harms, purportedly insufficient ‘to justify control’ (Bliss, 2016; Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs, 2013, p.4). This demonstrates how drugs policy extrapolated from ‘opinion rather than evidence’ (Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs, 2013, para.226) and marginalises communities. Like CRs, CWs and KWs will be recorded on local systems, not the police national computer (PNC), and can only be administered on admission of guilt (Byrne, 2009, para.3.4; Hayman, 2003, para.4.4 and 4.6).

Figure 1. Escalatory Framework for CWs (Byrne, 2009: 4)

The efficacy of cannabis possession policing is remarkably under-researched but does point toward ‘erratic patterns’ of CW application (Grace, Lloyd and Page, 2022, p.7). It is unsurprising as most cannabis policing is ‘accidental’- found in the course of unrelated policing activity (Lloyd, Page and Grace, 2018). Only a third of officers are aware of CW guidance, with some citizens receiving multiple warnings without evidence of escalation (Grace, Lloyd and Page, 2022, p.7; Lloyd *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, a third of officers believed that the smell of cannabis was sufficient for a search (Lloyd, Page and Grace, 2018, p.3), yet without ‘other contributory factors’ this will rarely be justification

(HMICFRS, 2017), and is used more on S&Ss of black individuals (section 2.6; College of Policing, 2023). This bias is visible in other areas: residents in deprived areas are more likely to have a CW issued, with evidence of under-policing of those from higher socioeconomic backgrounds (section 2.6.4; Grace, Lloyd and Page, 2022; Lloyd, Page and Grace, 2018, p.2)0. Possession of cannabis brings many individuals into their first ‘adversarial contact with the police. Therefore the scope for erosion of police legitimacy is obvious’ (May *et al.*, 2002, p.33). Fortunately CW and KW, comprise 1% of OOCs issued, they are on a steady decline from 9% in 2019, perhaps as officers feel they produce ineffective outcomes- ‘all we’d do is cost them money’ (Ministry of Justice, 2024b, p.6; Drugs Education Programme Officer P1, quoted in Viggiani, 2022, p.95).

3.3.3 Penalty Notices for Disorder

PNDs are also a lesser used OOCs (3%, Ministry of Justice, 2024b, p.6). They are a variety of FPN established by s.1-11 Criminal Justice and Police Act 2001 c.16 (CJPA) to combat ‘low-level, anti-social and nuisance offending’ (Ministry of Justice, 2014); many offences involving PNDs issue relate to alcohol consumption (see s.1 CJPA). PNDs prescribe a fixed penalty of £60 or £90, depending on the offence and its circumstance, to be paid within 21 days or it will be registered at a Magistrates Court for enforcement at 1.5 times the original penalty (Sentencing Council, ND). The public interest stage of the FCT must be satisfied, but PNDs do not require an admittance of guilt. Payment discharges liability to be convicted, but suspects can request a trial (Ministry of Justice, 2014, pp.4 and 21; Birtwistle, 2013, p.10). A PND-E can be used to oblige participation in an ‘educational course’, but this is not deemed appropriate for those with substance misuse difficulties (s.2A CJPA; *ibid*, p.21). A refusal to engage may result in prosecution (*ibid*, p.7-11). A PND does not constitute a criminal record but will be recorded on the PNC and may be disclosed as part of an enhanced Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) check (*ibid*, para.1.9).

3.3.4 Simple & Conditional Cautions

SCs (historically, a formal or police caution) and CCs are governed by section 10 of PACE Code C (Home Office, 2019) and comprise 23% of OOCs issued (Ministry of Justice, 2024b, p.6). SCs are a formal non-statutory warning, predominantly designed for summary, lower-level offences. They are available for all offences within s.17(4)(b) CJCA, except indictable, which are only eligible in exceptional circumstances, and limited either-way offences (s.17(2) and (3) CJCA; The Crown Prosecution Service, 2020). SCs require an admittance of guilt and agreement to the caution, including a signed record. A refusal may result in prosecution being pursued (Home Office, 2019, para.11.13 and 11.14; Ministry of Justice, 2013, paras6–9 and 23). SCs should not be used to secure an admission of guilt (Ministry of

Justice, 2013, para.21); the disposal is not designed for those who wish to contest culpability. A SC is not a conviction, but since 2008 it has fallen within the Rehabilitation of Offenders Act 1974 c.53 (ROA, s.8A and 9A) as immediately spent. SCs may appear on standard and enhanced DBS checks. There is no formal right of appeal, wrongful cautions can only be quashed by complaint against the administering force or by judicial review (Ministry of Justice, 2013, paras67 and 86–89).

CCs are a formal statutory OOC under S.22 Criminal Justice Act 2003 (CJA, also s.23(5) and s.24(2); Home Office, 2019, para.11.13 and 11.14). They have the same cautioning criteria as a SC, with public interest considerations detailed at paragraph 2.7 in the CC Code of Practice (s.23 CJA; Ministry of Justice, 2013). Here, the signed caution record is admissible. CCs have conditions attached which must be appropriate, proportionate, and achievable (Ministry of Justice, 2013, para.2.21), and may under s.22(3) CJA be motivated by:

- Reparative; (including apologising, repairing damage, or specified financial compensation (Ministry of Justice, 2013, para.2.16))
- Rehabilitative (*inter alia*, attendance of an addiction programme (*ibid*, para 2.15)) or;
- Punitive objectives (currently only financial penalties (s.23A CJA)).

Appropriateness is determined by a ‘problem solving’ approach to alter the offenders’ behaviour and, if possible, provide redress to the victim, with financial penalties a last resort if no reparative or rehabilitative conditions are appropriate or proportionate to the offence (Ministry of Justice, 2013, para.2.23 and 2.25). Conditions must be met with within 16-20 weeks to avoid criminal proceedings being commenced (*ibid*, paras.1.2 and 2.30-2.32; s.24(s) CJA). Initially, the decision to issue a CC was held by the CPS, limiting their use, but in April 2013 suitability was discharged to the local custody officer (Neyroud and Slothower, 2013).

3.4 Key Critiques of OOC’s Application in E&W

3.4.1 The Development of OOC Use in E&W

The OOC landscape has ‘evolved’ in recent decades (HM Government and College of Policing, 2014a, p.6). In this era of austerity (HMICFRS, 2014), OOCs are desirable due to their lower cost and ability to free-up police time for frontline duties and more ‘serious’ crime (Criminal Justice Joint

Inspection, 2011; Birtwistle, 2013, p.4). The expeditiousness of OOCs aligns with deterrent aims of punishment (section 2.2); key consequentialist philosopher Beccaria denotes that justice must be certain, swift, and proportionate (Harcourt, 2013). Durlauf and Nagin observed that it was certainty, rather than severity, that had a greater deterrent effect, particularly when partnered with haste (2011). Instant cautions appear to be more effective than deferred cautions (Giller and Tutt, 1987): multiple reviews of OOCs have recommended that they be 'as closely linked to the point of arrest as possible' (Harvey *et al.*, 2007, p.396; Neyroud, 2018).

OOC expansion of volume and over time has been 'largely uncontrolled' (Criminal Justice Joint Inspection, 2011, p.4), and OOCs have seen a 69.5% reduction in use between 2008-2023, (in the year ending June 2008 643,000 OOCs were administered, Ministry of Justice, 2012, p.5; cf in the year ending June 2023 196,000 were administered, Ministry of Justice, 2024b, p.6). Historically, informal disposals (CRs and CW/KWs) have not been included in criminal justice statistics, with CR data only collected on a voluntary basis until April 2014, despite being administered nationally since 2009 (Ministry of Justice, 2024b, p.6; Heydari, 2023; Taylor and Bond, 2012, p.9). Revisions to the crime statistics framework enabled their inclusion in full-year datasets from March 2016, where 120,700 CRs were recorded (a third of OOCs issued that year (Ministry of Justice, 2016, p.11)), suggesting reductions in OOC use are much greater than they *prima facie* appear.

A major critique of OOCs is their 'haphazard' application, with volume variations of up to 21% between forces (Magistrates' Association, 2022; Home Affairs Committee, 2015; Sosa, 2012, p.1). Piecemeal policy is responsible for this asymmetry; the current six-tier system was introduced in 2003 but was implemented fragmentally from 2003-2009 'and is complex as a result' (CC Lynne Owens in Ministry of Justice and Grayling, 2014). The launch of a national police incentive in 2004 saw OOCs equivalent to trial justice in performance figures, yet at a lesser time and cost, resulting in OOC's peak in 2007 (HM Government and College of Policing, 2014a, the 'Offences Brought to Justice' initiative (Home Office, 2004; Garside, 2004). The incentive was scrapped in 2008, leading to the declines in OOC use (Sosa, 2012). Moreover, in 2017, (less than a decade after the six-tier system was realised) moves to a two-tier system were encouraged to curb this 'postcode lottery' of application which has seen dichotomous application of OOCs in E&W (Glen, 2018, para.2.4; Home Affairs Committee, 2015, p.8).

3.4.2 The Utilisation of OOC's in E&W

This 'cautions culture' had led some to believe that 'offenders are walking away scot-free', with the public liable to view OOCs as a 'soft option' (HM Government and College of Policing, 2014a, p.8;

Ministry of Justice and Grayling, 2014; Hough *et al.*, 2013, tbl.3.7). Of the 25,780 sentenced on cannabis possession charges in 2011, 55.1% received a fine, 16.3% were given a community sentence, and only 0.91% were sentenced to immediate custody (Ward, 2013, pp.291–292). In 2016, 60% of those sentenced to an either way or summary non-motoring offence received a fine from court, and 7.9% were discharged or received a bind over (Glen, 2018, p.4). Similar outcomes to these are viable under PNDs and CCs but at a much heavier time and cost, both to the offender and the state (sections 2.5 - 2.7.1). A lack of public understanding has led political and police leaders to view OOCs as 'high stakes' (Peter Neyroud at 02:10 Allen, Neyroud and Dhaliwal, n.d.), inherently stagnating policy development. The lacuna of voter understanding may be due to a lack of police transparency; only 14% of constabulary websites provide a definition of OOCs (Magistrates' Association, 2022; Shaw, 2022, p.75). When partnered with its 'organic' development (CC Lynne Owens in Ministry of Justice and Grayling, 2014), public misconception is understandable.

Further difficulties in OOCs' application include the absence of formal agreements between police and NHS Liaison & Diversion services (LaDS), who inform on treatment and rehabilitative conditions available in partner organisations (NHS Trust, 2022; Glen, 2018, p.14). However LaDS have no formalised remit nor archive of services, suffering from the same fragmented development as OOCs (Bradley, 2009, pp.81–82). These partner organisations lack formal agreements with police and LaDS (Lurigio, 2000), despite drugs-offending diversion schemes purportedly being 'partnership initiatives established between police, local healthcare organisations and drugs services' (Viggiani, 2022, p.4). In contrast, diversion in the USA is primarily mandated by the court as an alternative to custodial sentencing. Whilst outside the pre-prosecution models discussed, in a meta-analysis of diversion and Class A drug users, services and procedures were found to be of higher quality (Hayhurst *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, OOCs could benefit from a structured relationship with between partner organisations and legal agents.

3.4.3 Concerns of Net-widening

OOCs can bring individuals into contact with the CJS who otherwise would not have been which is termed 'net-widening' (Ofori, 2022; Cohen, 1985, pp.52–53). For instance, an Australian scheme targeting cannabis users saw a 280% increase in individuals processed in drug courts (Ali *et al.*, 1998). OOCs are a de-escalation from arrest and following orthodox punishments, visible in the requirement to meet the evidential FCT stage by higher level OOCs (PNDs, SCs, and CCs (see section 3.2.1)), and prerequisite of guilt for informal OOCs (CRs and CW/KWs). OOCs should only be used to 'down-tariff'; when there is sufficient evidence to bring greater criminal justice interventions against the

suspect. Prior to CWs, a depenalisation scheme was run in the Lambeth, London (depenalisation going one step further than decriminalisation to removing all criminal and civil penalties). This resulted in a 29.3% increase in cannabis-related recorded crime. This had long-term impacts: following the scheme cannabis crime rates were 61.0% higher than the London average (Adda, McConnell and Rasul, 2014). During the debate to reclassify cannabis to Class C (section 2.4.1) experts forewarned that it may 'backfire' if formal warnings were issued when informal warnings would have previously been used (May *et al.*, 2002, p.51). Therefore, there is a risk that OOCs may draw drug-users into our damaging system of prohibition.

A further example is the broadening of PNDs to include s.5 Public Order Act 1986 into PND's domain (by the Criminal Justice and Police Act 2001 (Amendment) Order, SI No. 2002/1934), which witnessed greater numbers of PNDs issued than prosecutions would have been pursued at the magistrates court (Grace, 2014). Arguments of 'polification', where police remit is expanded to tasks which are better undertaken by the partner organisations they outsource to (Kemshall and Maguire, 2001), are debateable as police can be hesitant to engage in 'social work' activities (Worden and McLean, 2018). A study by the Police Foundation demonstrates how police perceptions of their role change over time from Crime or Public Service Related, to Safeguarding, which the author terms a 'reality shock' (Charman, 2018, p.4). This results in 'longstanding and geographically widespread' cynicism in officers, particularly those with an authoritarian personality, who are hesitant to engage in helping vulnerable people: "*it's just constant mopping up of people, who literally, cannot run their own lives*" (Officer D10 in *ibid*, p.6). Building on this and section 2.6.4 on police discretion, OOCs conjure concerns of police being 'judge and jury' (Grace, 2014, p.75). Police could be considered gatekeepers to support services (in addition to the CJS), controlling who is diverted from orthodox responses to potential support (Lymperopoulou, 2023; McAra and McVie, 2010). This has led some to refer to diversion as 'deserving' justice (Zane and Mears, 2023, as touched on in section 2.6.4). Moreover, OOC participation may be limited if police are not seen as trustworthy 'brokers' (Goetz and Mitchell, 2006, p.505). Koning advances this as 'diffuse' policing, an agent of the institutional landscape for 'problematic' or 'at-risk' populations, whose 'soft' or informal measures marry welfare to discipline (de Koning, 2017, p.538). This results in certain populations being enveloped in a 'sticky net of surveillance' (*ibid*), reminiscent of the plight of children in care (section 2.6.3). Although, actions of police forces have contributed to novel adaptations (see section 4.2), such as OOCs, in light of the human cost of the 'war on drugs' (Bacon, 2022).

3.4.4 Racial Disparity and Guilty Pleas

As detailed in Section 2, the relationship between police and BAME communities is often antagonistic. Due to the distrust of police, BAME defendants are consistently more likely to plead 'not guilty', with Black and Asian men one and a half times more likely than white defendants, a phenomena which has been observed since the 1990s (Bowen, 2017; Lammy MP, 2017, p.26; Uhrig, 2016, tbl.5.3; Flood-Page and Mackie, 1998). The CJS incentives guilty pleas, *inter alia*, reducing custodial sentences by a third (Sentencing Council, 2017), or as eligible for informal OOCs (CRs and CW/KWs). This will likely result in OOC up-tariffing for BAME defendants, who are already over-policed in the drugs policy arena.

The 'onerous' and 'unhelpful' pre-condition of guilty pleas results in unnecessary contact with the CJS (Cushing, 2014, p.141). This was addressed by experimental pilots trialling deferred prosecution models, in particular the landmark Turning Point (TP), and further Chance to Change (C2C) pilot (Kinsella, Williams and Wong, 2023; Neyroud and Slothower, 2013). TP did not require guilt for the application of their OOC, which resulted in a demographic profile comparable to the area, rather than disproportionate BAME, and had particular success in reducing reoffending for young black men (Neyroud, 2014, 2021; Lammy MP, 2017). C2C built on this; the London site allowed suspects to access services offering support on employment, housing, mentoring, and (where relevant) substance misuse (Kinsella, Williams and Wong, 2023). Whilst the small cohort prevents conclusions to its impact on ethnic disparity, the removal of guilt contributed towards 'addressing the trust deficit' between the police, CJS, and BAME aggregates, and was also viewed positively the officer practitioners of the scheme (*ibid*, p.13-14). The requirement of a guilty plea in the wake of this evidence raises questions as to the exegesis of this pre-condition, if it does not benefit the offender or society through a reduction of reoffending. It demonstrates a need to cling to ideological reasoning through expressivism, and retributivism as moral acceptance is a requirement of punishment within this school of thought.

3.5 Conclusion

OOCs application in E&W is complex and discordant. Its organic development has resulted in a poorly recorded system, which varies inter-force-area, resulting in a postcode lottery of diversion. The main types of OOC issued vary in their burden on the suspect and may not be best suited for the offences they are aimed at. Due to the lacuna of reliable data, it is difficult to assess how much net-widening is occurring within E&W, yet requirements of guilt mean many BAME individuals are caught in a criminal justice net they are undeserving of. It is evident that reform is needed to ensure equality in application, and better improve public understanding, and thus support, for this developing arm of criminal justice.

Chapter 4: The Application Of Out-of-court-disposals To Drugs-related Offending

This section aims to address the ‘heterogeneity’ of diversion studies in E&W, as this ‘renders authoritarian comparisons... difficult to achieve’ (Harvey *et al.*, 2007, p.385). In the fractured climate of drug policy, it is unsurprising that there are no set frameworks for policy makers to design OOCs within (Stevens *et al.*, 2022; McLean, 2018). This is the derivation of the author’s systematic analysis (see Appendix A). On the basis of this research, the TTPF proposed by s.98-121 PCSCA will be examined, alongside previous NPCC recommendations (Glen, 2018, p.8), to discover if this new framework will improve on the current piecemeal delivery of OOCs in E&W.

4.1 OOC Trials in E&W

4.1.1 Other Reviews of Diversion Schemes

Whilst there are several reviews of diversion practices (Stevens *et al.*, 2022; Weir *et al.*, 2022; Lindquist-Grantz *et al.*, 2021; Hayhurst *et al.*, 2019; Harvey *et al.*, 2007), Stevens et al notes these typically focus on specific models, the theoretical provenance of reform, or certain outcomes (2022, p.30-31), none of which will answer the hypothesis posed in this dissertation. Whilst Blais et al. (2022) focused on drug users in ‘police-led’ (rather than civilian-initiated (Kopak and Gleicher, 2020)) ‘prebooked’ (pre-charge (Case *et al.*, 2009)) diversion, none of the twenty-seven studies examined operated in E&W, where 77.1% of forces are currently developing or delivering drug diversion schemes (27 out of 35 forces who responded to a NPCC national survey, Slade, 2022, p.2).

Consequently, the author has constructed several themes in her systematic analysis of eight studies within E&W; *inter alia*, guilt requirements, research quality, and retention. The key outcome will be reoffending rates as the key indicator of these studies efficacy in relation to orthodox criminal justice approaches (section 2.7.2). These will illuminate how OOCs can best be applied in the context of drugs-relating offending in E&W.

4.1.2 Study Designs of OOCB Trials in E&W

Within experimental OOCB practice in E&W, two fundamental models dominated: those replicating the deferred prosecution scheme (DP) in Birmingham's TP (five out of the eight studies in the systematic analysis), and an amended CR structure originating in Thames Valley's Drug Diversion Pilot (DDP, two of the eight studies).

To apply TP's DP scheme, satisfaction of the FCT evidential stage was required; as guilt was not a prerequisite, under aims of combatting racial inequality (section 3.3.4), within the systematic review, this was only prevalent in one other study: Durham's Checkpoint.³ The scheme required willing candidates to sign a four-month contracting stating they would not reoffend, alongside further conditions based on a personalised needs assessment, *inter alia*, restorative justice, drug treatment. On successful completion of the contract, a NFA was issued, with non-compliance or refusal to participate resulting in prosecution for the original (and any subsequent) offences.

The CR scheme, initiated by DDP, referred eligible individuals in possession of a controlled drug (within s.5 MDA) to drug-service provider Cranstoun for three educational sessions (Cranstoun, n.d.). Refusal to partake resulted in administration of other criminal justice mechanisms, including other OOCBs.

4.1.3 Trials Research Quality, including comparison of Participation Criteria

Outcomes from OOCBs can take a variety of forms and journeys (Stevens *et al.*, 2022, fig.2), yet this does not excuse the inconsistency of reporting relevant factors visible in Appendix A. OOCB studies often have 'poor methodological quality and inadequate reporting' (Harvey *et al.*, 2007, p.385 (mentioned across the aforementioned reviews)), *per contra*, 'in policing, getting decisions wrong matters' (Slothower, 2014, p.353). The poor scientific quality was addressed in Turning Point (TP), where randomised control trials (RCT) were used to create directly comparable, and thus internally valid, diverted group and control (Stevens *et al.*, 2022, p.46; Neyroud and Slothower, 2013, p.3). This design was only applied in the following Checkpoint study therefore the results of the systematic review cannot be exempt from selection bias, with multiple citing officer discretion as factor in the eligibility process (DEP and Divert- see Appendix A). As discussed in sections 2.6.4 and 3.4.4, this risks discrimination. On Viggiani's report on the Drugs Education Pilot (DEP), their application mirrors the disproportion of BAME individuals also seen in arrest statistics (2022, p.21).

³ Although, information for this was unable to be gathered for two of the eight studies.

There is also heterogeneity in the eligibility of offence inter-scheme; many prioritise ‘low-level’ (DDP, Checkpoint Plus, DivertC, DIVERTWM), or ‘low-harm’ incidents (TP), with the assumption that low-level offenders will be better served by OOCs (Neyroud, 2015). Not only does this provide unequal samples between study’s cohorts and controls, but is a *de facto* incorrect assumption. The opposite has been observed by commentators and within the cohort (Hoff *et al.*, 1999). Checkpoint purposely included a ‘moderate-risk’ cohort, but after bringing in a lower-risk cohort in the RCT stage of the project, saw no difference in reoffending during the contract (5% (Hogg, 2017, p.3)), and saw a completion rate of 90% (higher than the cohort average (see section 4.2.4 and Appendix A)). Therefore the current approach, and proposed ‘low-level’ two-tier framework (Heydari, 2023), may be limiting OOCs application.

4.1.4 Programme Retention

Enforced drug programmes tend to work ‘particularly’ well (Neyroud and Slothower, 2013, p.15); high levels of coercion have been associated with increased programme completion rates, and thus improved outcomes for desistance from reoffending and drug use (Hayhurst *et al.*, 2019; Harvey *et al.*, 2007, p.385; Broner, Mayrl and Landsberg, 2005). However, it is to be noted that some have questioned the ethics of such an approach (e.g., Harvey *et al.*, 2007, p.385). In this field, a retention rate of 60% is impressive (*ibid*), which appears to be exceeded in all but one study (DPP, *cf* TP and DEP did not publish retention data). Rates may be determined by the drug programme’s efficacy, for instance, services which also incorporate social support have greater appeal (Lammy MP, 2017; Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs, 2016). This impact of holistic conditions within OOCs can be seen in the systematic analysis. Studies which employed a ‘needs assessment’, *ergo* tailored conditions, had completion rates of 82%< (Checkpoint, Checkpoint Plus, Pathfinder, and DivertC), whereas DDP and DIVERT, with only one condition of session(s) on drug education/use, saw completion rates of 42 and 71% respectively (see Appendix A). Therefore, OOCs which aim to combat multiple barriers to stability and desistance are more likely to see engagement.

4.1.5 Reoffending Rates in OOC Trials

To reach this dissertation’s research aims, considering the impact of OOCs on reoffending rates is crucial to assess them as a mechanism for reducing crime. Harvey *et al* concluded there was ‘tentative evidence that diversion, in particular, can result in reduced criminal recidivism’ (2007, p.385). In Blais *et al*’s systematic review, 67% of the studies found favourable outcomes for criminal recidivism (2022, p.9). The current reoffending rate for E&W is 25.8% (Ministry of Justice, 2024c), in comparison to 16.2% for OOCs issued under the current six-tier system (Sturrock and Mews, 2018, p.5 (due to the absence of consistent reporting of OOCs, the last comprehensive data set analysed was 2014-2015)). Due to

the lacuna of consistent data, there is insufficient ‘robust’ evidence to demonstrate the mechanisms utility to reduce reoffending (Shaw, 2022, p.102). However, OOCs appear more effective than court appearances, as those who received a SC reoffend at a rate 15% lesser than those who received a court fine (court fine reoffending rate 30%, cf SC 15%, see Ratcliffe, 2022), therefore justifying their use above the limited power of the Magistrates Court to satisfy utilitarian ideals. Regarding the systematic review, Pathfinder reported 85.5% of attendees were motivated to ‘avoid being involved in crime in future’ (Goodall *et al.*, n.d., para.2.3.5), with the studies having a mean reoffending rate of 10.35% (see Table 1). This demonstrates that OOCs are a cost-effective, lower harm alternative to orthodox methods of punishment and with greater success under deterrent aims of criminal justice (Barnham, Spyt and Kew, n.d.).

Studies (outlined in Appendix A) ⁴	Reoffending rate (within 1 year) (%)	
	Study Cohort	OOC control
Checkpoint, Durham	14.6	21.9
Checkpoint Plus, Surrey	6.3	16.3
DEP, Avon & Somerset	23	
Pathfinder, Devon & Cornwall	3	
DDP, Thames Valley	8.7	
DivertC, Cleveland	5.85	
DIVETWM, West Midlands & Mercia	11 (re-arrest)*	

Figure 2. Table to show, Reoffending Rate within a year of systematic review cohort (*within six months)

⁴ TP failed to publish figures, so the author has omitted DP from this table, however Neyroud has stated in multiple instances that there were ‘reductions’ in reoffending.

4.1.6 Reattendance and Drug Use: it's importance to OCCD trials

Addiction recovery is a long and difficult journey, with an average of 12 'quit attempts' for cocaine and 9.5 for heroin, as many suffer from 'chronic relapse' (Sogbesan *et al.*, 2024, p.3; Kelly *et al.*, 2019, p.2). Similar to the development of drug addiction (section 2.5.1), various idiosyncratic and environmental factors affect recovery, including 'drug use consequences' such as criminal justice interventions, which are positively associated with attempts to quit (Sogbesan *et al.*, 2024). Thus, for drugs-sensitive diversion, reattendance is a crucial element, as acknowledged by the DPP scheme's creators (Spyt, Barnham and Kew, 2019). *Per contra*, the current OCCD framework in E&W is not designed for repeat offenders (Home Affairs Committee, 2015).

Checkpoint saw a completion rate of 90% overall, but 30% for those on a drugs-use pathway who could not reattend. OCCDs incorporating drug-sensitive conditions can encourage users towards desistance, but the current escalatory model is not adapted to best meet this aggregate. Three schemes in the systematic review (Checkpoint Plus, DDP, and DIVERT) acknowledged this nuance by allowing attendance to be repeated (if conditions were met). In DIVERT, there was a repeat referral rate of 6.3%. In DDP, it is described as 'both a carrot and a stick' to ensure compliance with their amended CR model. The 'stick' is the consequence of more intensive CJS mechanisms encourages compliance to the CR and drug education sessions, and the 'carrot' being that participants have the opportunity to repeat the system again if they abide the condition (France and Barrow-Grint, 2019, pp.47–48). France and Barrow-Grint outlines its importance for three reasons:

- Pragmatically, the individual may not be able to attend the three sessions before they are reprimanded again;
- Treatment is not an instantaneous process e.g., issuance of medication; and
- Addiction may see many attempts and relapses (*ibid*, p.48).

Within the current six-tier system, such conditions can only be imposed at the extremities of the OCCD scale: CRs, where they cannot be enforced, and CCs, where they will be monitored. As less than 20% of individuals experiencing addiction to Class As receive treatment (Ronsley *et al.*, 2020), the current OCCD framework is a missed opportunity for a gateway to health and social support, which would alleviate offending under the drugs/ crime nexus.

4.2 The PCSCA's two-tier framework

4.2.1 The Law & draft Code of Practice

The PCSCA (ss.98-121) is poised to abolish the current 'unwieldy' OOC framework OOCs (S.208(1) PCSCA; The Police, Crime, Sentencing and Courts Act 2022 (Commencement No. 7) Regulations 2023 (SI 2023/573); Damien Hinds, Ministry of Justice, 2023, foreword). The proposed TTPF, comprised of upper-tier diversionary cautions (DC), and lower-tier community cautions (CCP) (s.98(1) and s.118 PCSCA) aims to provide a 'simplified, consistent approach across' E&W (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.16). CCPs will be issued when prosecution would not serve public interest, otherwise DCs will be used (*ibid*, para.2.2). The title of 'two-tier' is a misnomer, as the non-statutory disposal CRs will remain (*ibid*, page 5). Experiments with a two-tier system (CRs and CCs) commissioned by the MoJ between 2014-2015 found the move to the two-tier system did not alter the likelihood of OOC prescription,⁵ with forces recommended to move towards it in 2018 (Glen, 2018, p.8).

CCPs can apply to summary and either-way offences, including possession, with DCs applied to indictable-only offences only in exceptional circumstances (s.99(3) PCSCA, Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.2.3, 5.1, 5.3 and Annex C). Cases must satisfy the evidential FCT stage, consent to the caution, admit guilt, and *prima facie* have no reliable defences (DC: s.99(2) and CPP: s.108(2) PCSCA, Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.517(a)). The applicable conditions are categorised into rehabilitation and reparation (DC: s.101 and see s.100(2), and CCP: s.110 and see s.109(2) PCSCA), and financial (as the only punitive condition (DC: s.102, and CCP: s.111 PCSCA Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.1.3). DCs can also result in deportation for 'relevant foreign offenders', critiques of which are beyond the scope of discussion of this paper (s.103(2)(a) and s.103(4) PCSCA; such as those already viable for a deportation order under sch.5 and s.5, Immigration Act 1971 c.77.; s.10, Immigration and Asylum Act 1999 c.33). Both formalise victim consultation through 'community remedy documents', *inter alia*, restorative justice (DC: s.100(5), and CCP: s.109(5) PCSCA), following NPCC recommendations (Glen, 2018, p.8). A breach of CCP conditions 'without reasonable excuse' (s.105(1) and s.115(2) PCSCA) will result in imposition of financial penalties or accessory of further conditions (s.98(5)(b) and s.115(2) *ibid*). For DCs this can also instigate prosecution for the offence (s.98(5)(a) and s.105(1) *ibid* (alike DP models previously discussed

⁵ Records in the pilot area prior to the pilot were 59% were Community Resolutions (CRs) and 41% were Conditional Cautions (CCs). Over the same period the counterfactual sites recorded a total of 13,273 OOCs, of which 55% were CRs, PNDs or Cannabis/Khat Warnings and 45% were Simple Cautions or CCs (Ames and others, 2018, p.3).

in section 4.2.1)). Cautions may be prohibited when one or more has already been issued, including CCs and others issued within the six-tier statutory model (s.117(1) and (3) PCSCA).

The draft Code of Practice (CoP),⁶ however, only ‘paints half the picture’, as it only includes guidance on DCs and CCPs, not CRs or NFA/Outcome 22s, which could have been placed on a statutory footing by the PCSCA (Slade, 2023, p.1). Whilst outside the MoJ’s remit, pragmatically the code of practice is a ‘missed opportunity’ for guidance on the full framework (*ibid*, p.5). Although, a limited comparison is offered (see Appendix B) and questions outlined for officers on when ‘on-the-spot’ CRs should be offered (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.3.4). This neglects the NPCC’s 2018 recommendations to provide ‘clear and simplified guidance’ and a ‘clear framework’ for OOCs (Glen, 2018, p.8). As acknowledged by Slade at the Centre for Justice Innovation, the CoP is a ‘general overview’, lacking ‘considerable detail’ (Slade, 2023, p.3), therefore it is challenging to draw full conclusions of what the TTPF may look like in practice.

4.2.2 Systemic Racism Appears Unaddressed in the TTPF

Under the TTPF, only CRs can be applied without admittance of guilt, and the CoP suggests those who give no-comment interviews face a blanket refusal to OOC administration (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.5.25, 5.27 and 5.34). As acknowledged by the landmark Lammy Review and, *inter alia*, TP (see section 3.3.4), this is a mechanism which disadvantages BAME suspects, and will lead to a disproportionate number up-tariffed to prosecution (sections 3.4.4 and 4.2.3). The NPCC have recommended greater autonomy and discretion for issuing officers (Glen, 2018, p.8), which could further scope for bias. Conversely, it is limited in the CoP, yet this is without consideration of offences which disproportionality effect BAME communities. For example, possession of a bladed weapon is excluded in the TTPF, resulting in up-tariffing for those caught, despite an annual average of 3,100 OOCs issued for possession of a weapon between 2011-2021 (Slade, 2023, p.7). *Ergo*, it appears the TTPF will worsen racial disproportionality in the CJS, and usurp aims of the OOC system to help to repair relationships between the police and community (Viggiani, 2022; Blanco, 2021).

4.2.3 TTPF and Drug-users

The TTPF faces the same issues of eligibility and reattendance as previous studies (see section 4.2.4), as ‘sufficient time’ (12-24 months) must elapse to re-issue a caution. It places weight on ‘patterns of long-term offending’, ignoring the NPCC’s key ‘success factor’ of greater focus on rehabilitative

⁶ Issued by the secretary of state under s.116(3) PCSCA, the finalised Code was expected to be published on the 24th of May 2024; Ministry of Justice, 2023.

conditions (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.4.3 and 4.5(a); Glen, 2018, p.8). Cautions may no-longer be issued when rehabilitative routes have been 'exhausted', but the CoP fails to define what this may mean for OOCd decision-makers (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.4.4(h)). For drugs offences, this will result in more arrests and prosecutions than schemes such as DDP, as desistance does not exist in a 'binary state of succeed or fail' (Slade, 2023, p.6). Furthermore, the CoP does consider the 'legacy' OOCds (those under the current six-tier system) where conditions were not attached (SCs, CW/KWs, and PNDs), whilst stating compliance with conditions may be favourable for reattendance but fails to delineate this (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.4.4(c) and (f)). This suggests repeat participation in the OOCd framework will likely be subject to 'deserving' justice (see section 4.6.4).

CCPs can be applied to drug offences, excluding intent to supply and import/ export of Class As (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.5.3, 5.8(g) and Annex C). However, Slade proposes that all individuals found in possession of a controlled drug (under s.5(1) MDA) should not be eligible for a CCP or DC, but a CR (Slade, 2023, p.7). This would enable issuance of multiple CRs without a criminal record and its accompanying stigmatisation, further stating that the conditions attached to the CCP or DC render it 'too onerous' for most possession cases (*ibid*, p.8). The PCSCA's TTPF does not address the nuances of drug-related offending, particularly in instances of addiction, which will deepen trauma and incur unnecessary costs for the CJS.

4.2.4 OOCd Conditions under the TTPF

At least one 'appropriate, proportionate, and achievable' condition must be attached to a CCP and a DC (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.6.20-6.25). The CoP fails to define these adjectives, only stating they must be able to be completed within sixteen weeks in summary-only cases (*ibid*, para.6.27). The TTPF follows the needs assessment used prior, recommending a 'problem-solving' approach be taken identifying suitable conditions (*ibid*, para.6.4). Conversely, there is little elaboration on the 'needs assessment', therefore, procedure and intention, or whether arbiters should be assessing risk or what criminogenic needs, are obscure (Ames *et al.*, 2018, p.3). Ames *et al.* and TP, *inter alia*, highlighted that officers struggled to set conditions due to limiting training or complex case circumstances/ needs (*ibid*, Neyroud and Slothower, 2015; Slothower, 2014). This is unaddressed in the new framework.

The CCP and DC have scope to 'tackle' substance misuse with rehabilitative conditions, such as the drugs education sessions in the systematic review (DC: s.101(3)(c), s.101(6), and s.101(7); CCP: s.110(3)(c), s.110(6), and s.110(7) PCSCA; Damien Hinds, Hinds, 2023, foreword; Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.6.5(b)). However, under TTPF, the offender may be required to cover the cost (Ministry of

Justice, 2023, para.6.5(b)). This raises ethical questions on access to justice (Slade, 2023, p.8), marginalised groups including homeless individuals will be unable to afford to abide their caution, and thus will be prosecuted for poverty. The CoP states that financial penalties should not be 'more attractive' to the offenders than that incurred by rehabilitative conditions (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.7.6), demonstrating the illogic of attaching a condition, which is otherwise considered punitive (s.102 and s.111 PCSCA; *ibid*, para1.3), to a rehabilitative condition. Under the long-understood nexus of acquisitive crime and drug use (section 2.5.2) this imposition seems ill-considered and counterproductive, a significant call for concern regarding the TTPF.

Restrictive conditions include prohibition of criminal conduct, but the CoP fails to state time-limits (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.6.5(e)). Financial penalties (£100 for summary/ either-way offences, and £150 for indictable (DC only) must be paid within 28 days or be increased by 50%, with a possibility it may proceed to enforcement at Magistrates Court (s.111 PCSCA; *ibid*, paras.7.10, 7.11 and 7.14). Court fine repayments, whilst averaging higher rates, are means-tested (to an extent), yet still see average payment rates of 50% over 12 months (s.35 Sentencing Act 2020 c.17; Bowen, 2024, pp.8 and 21); it seems unlikely that a 28-window will achieve greater success. However, the current 21-day-window under PNDs has seen similar success (51%, Halligan-Davis and Spicer, 2004; Roberts, 2005). Yet, this research is outdated and does not reflect the financial difficulties rampant in contemporary E&W. Those who are economically disadvantaged are thus more likely to breach their CCP and, amongst other consequences, be ineligible for an OOC in the future.

DCs are not enforced by fines, failure to comply results in prosecution if the FCT is still met on reapplication (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.7.15 and 9.34). The suspects signed DC document (including admission of guilt) will be admissible at trial (s.99(2)(e) PCSCA; *ibid*, para.9.13). Ames et al. found some conditions to be unsubstantial to the offender nor supported desistance, and recommended resources to assist with compliance monitoring, echoed by the NPCC (Ames *et al.*, 2018, p.3; Glen, 2018). With the outcomes for non-compliance of DC in mind, it is of serious concern that methods for monitoring such compliance is not clearly delineated with the CoP (Ministry of Justice, 2023, para.9.23-9.28)- will one missed session be considered non-compliance, will three? These boundaries must be established to ensure the TTPF is workable, and, most importantly, within the rule of law.

4.2.5 Application Concerns

Whilst the new framework is unlikely to alter the volume of OOCs administered,⁷ there are concerns of ‘up-tariffing’, with a snowball effect on reoffending (Ofori, 2022). In Ames et al.’s assessment of a two-tier system, CCs constituted 31% of OOCs in counterfactual areas, whereas in the pilot they nearly doubled to 59%. The authors propose this is due to SC and PND ‘conversion’ (Ames et al., 2018, pp.42–43), but with the DP model employed by DC, this is now of much greater consequences for those who fail conditions. Therefore, the TTPF may see more offenders undergoing prosecution for offences which previously would have incurred a low-level OOC, increasing interactions with orthodox punishment.

4.3 Conclusion

The new system does address the piecemeal nature of OOCs, and encourages consistency, yet the PCSCA is a missed opportunity for addressing racial disparity and the nuances of drugs-related offending. The imposition of funds for rehabilitative conditions is removed from academic and historic understandings of those policed under this mechanism and will significantly reduce the TTPF’s efficacy for drugs-related offending. Finally, the CoP is incomplete in establishing a pragmatic framework. It is to be hoped that the upcoming Code of Practice reflects these issues, as *prima facie*, the TTPF does little to improve the contemporary OOC landscape.

⁷ Records in the pilot area prior to the pilot were 59% were Community Resolutions (CRs) and 41% were Conditional Cautions (CCs). Over the same period the counterfactual sites recorded a total of 13,273 OOCs, of which 55% were CRs, PNDs or Cannabis/Khat Warnings and 45% were Simple Cautions or CCs (Ames and others, 2018, p.3).

Chapter 5: Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

This dissertation set out to explore whether OOCDS are more effective in reducing drugs-related offending and harms than traditional prosecution measures. The political foundations of domestic drugs prohibition demonstrated the ideological construction of illicit drug use under the MDA, and that this has bled into drugs policing, harming individuals, and communities. The efficacy of the CJS was analysed through the lens of orthodox justifications of punishment: retribution, utilitarianism, and expressivism. Chapter 2 concludes that the current penal approach exacerbates the courts and prison crisis, perpetuating drug harms and recidivism.

To analyse the benefits and limitations of OOCDS, Ch.2 finds OOCDS a stronger mechanism for reducing drugs-related offending than orthodox methods, *inter alia*, due to their ability to address causes of offending. However, OOCDS complex practice due to piecemeal policy is delineated, with their organic development resulting in unequal application. OOCDS may cause net-widening, and do not combat systemic racism present in the wider CJS, particularly in drugs policing. OOCDS require further innovation to best address drugs-related offending.

The final aim of this dissertation was to assess the changes to E&W's OOCDS framework proposed by the TTPF under s.98-121 PCSCA. A systematic analysis was conducted to assess variations of OOCDS practice in relation to drugs cases, concluding that experimental frameworks which prioritised needs assessments and holistic conditions, including drug education programmes, were more effective at reducing reoffending (10.4%), under comparison to the current OOCDS framework (16.2%) and custodial sentences (58.3%). While poor research methods compromise their validity, the cohort further demonstrates that OOCDS can be delivered in manners sensitive to BAME and drug-using communities. This in-depth analysis delineated the needs of a new OOCDS framework, enabling scrutiny of the PCSCA and its draft CoP. Whilst the proposed framework will remove the piecemeal and inconsistent nature of current OOCDS practice, it negates prior recommendations, which could further decrease drugs-related harms and reoffending in E&W.

5.2 Implications & Recommendations

This dissertation benefits drafters of the final CoP and law enforcement practitioners by discussing the current pitfalls of OOCDS and how they could be amended the new framework. However, the draft CoP

is insufficient in its detail and consideration of academic and third-sector commentary on OOC reform. This oversight implies that the legislature's current understanding of best OOC practice is incomplete, or in the history of the reception of drug-using and ethnic minority communities, potentially wilfully ignorant. The new framework is likely to see more prosecutions brought *ergo*, the TTPF may not alter the overall volume change to OOCs issued but may have severe consequences for individuals and communities caught in the increased up-tariffing.

To combat this, and racial disproportionality, the new CoP should remove the ban on no-comment interviews being ineligible for OOCs. The evidential FCT stage should replace this prerequisite to ensure cases are of sufficient candour for OOCs. This would improve disparities for BAME individual's entry to the CJS and prevent unnecessary arrests and prosecutions. At the very least, police discretion should be monitored more closely, and application arbiters available to scrutinise, as the CoP is remiss in its vague outline of the new framework.

The imposition of self-finance for rehabilitative conditions is also highly problematic. It should be removed from the final CoP to ensure equal access to justice for those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. It reflects policymakers' inability to ensure the implementation aligns with academic understandings of the drugs/crime nexus. The result will be inhibition of OOCs in viable contexts, and preventable failures of DC and CCP conditions, likely incurring inappropriate prosecutions. Self-finance of rehabilitative conditions is another key factor to be amended by the upcoming CoP.

Finally, the absence of guidance on setting conditions will likely repeat inconsistencies seen within the current system. In the absence of a clear national framework for police to operate within, then the TTPF will repeat the detrimental organic development of the current OOC system, thus undermining its main aim of unifying forces in E&W in one system. Guidance on setting conditions was a key factor outlined by the NPCC as early as 2018, but *prima facie* this has not been realised practically. TP developed models which could be employed to assist consistency in OOC's procedure in the final CoP. Therefore, the CoP should include CRs and NFA/Outcome 22s to ensure the full range of OOCs are understood and provides one document for deciding law enforcement agents to reference.

5.3 Future Research

Whilst full conclusions on the future of OOCs in E&W cannot be drawn until the final CoP is released, this dissertation provides a useful framework to assess its practice. The systematic analysis delineates where police innovation in this field has transpired and outlines the current research limitations. Due

to the piecemeal nature of the six-tier system, it is difficult to assess the full picture of the framework nationwide. However, the TTPF provides potential for a clean slate. If policymakers and government agents properly harness this development, future research could be reliably conducted, ensuring continuing evolution of CJS techniques for the greater protection of individuals and society. This is an opportunity to advance beyond the fifty-year stagnation of drug policy, helping to implement harm-reduction outcomes which better reflect contemporary understandings.

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Appendix A

The systematic analysis excluded projects with a national reach, such as [Druglink](#)ⁱⁱ or project [ADDER](#).ⁱⁱ Those focusing on youth interventions were excluded, resulting in twelve *prima facie* eligible studies. Of these, three were exempt as they had a sole focus on women,ⁱⁱⁱ which dissertation does not have sufficient scope examine in the requisite detail. One further diversion scheme, C2C was excluded; while a report detailed some of the research design, it was narrative rather than research,^{iv} and therefore lacked sufficient data for inclusion in the analysis.

Study	OOCD applied	Eligibility	Study Design	Guilt	Completion/Retention	Proven Reoffending Rates	Option to reattend
<i>Turning Point</i> (TP), ^v Birmingham, 2011-2014	DP	Suspects ineligible for an informal resolution, but other OOCD, and the offence would not result in prison, with no more than one previous conviction (' low-harm ') Incident must satisfy the FCT	Randomised low (50/50 with a control) suspects asked to attend a meeting >72hrs post-offence to ask if they wished to participate in the trial. On agreement the 'TP contract' is signed, which lasts four months, and concerns bespoke conditions following a needs assessment. Conditions <i>inter alia</i> , restorative justice, drug courses, with the mandatory condition to not reoffend. On completion, a NFA was issued. Non-compliance would result in prosecution for the original and any subsequent offences.	No	No data	No figure, but 'reductions' in reoffending	No- Failure to complete adhere to the contract results in a note on the police gateway to not be reapplied.
<i>Checkpoint</i> , ^{vi} Durham, 2015- present	DP	Suspects with less than three-previous offences- aimed at 'moderate risk' offenders Also, higher level of offence severity- but must not be graded 'high risk' in forecasting models	Followed TP's study design, checkpoint expanded the design to the whole of Durham constabulary and had a wider cohort of suspects	No	90% completed their contract, but only one third of those on the drugs pathway completed	Reoffending rate of (14.6%) in comparison to OOCD control (21.9%)	No

<p>Cohort: 55% no previous offending, 30% 1-3 previous offences, 15% 4 or more (an error)</p>	<p>DP</p>	<p>'Low-level' offences</p>	<p>Based on Durham's Checkpoint</p>	<p>No info</p>	<p>95% during the all-female cohort 2018-2019</p>	<p>Checkpoint plus graduates reoffending rates 6.3% compared to 25% of previous year</p> <p>Reduced reoffending compared to OOCDC control 10%.</p>	<p>Aimed at those with repeat contact with the CJS</p>
<p>Checkpoint Plus, Surrey, 2016-now^{vii}</p>	<p>Alternative</p>	<p>Irrespective of previous offending</p> <p>At the point of arrest, discretion of officer</p> <p>Administered in the instance of being caught in possession of illegal drugs (within limitations of, <i>inter alia</i>, active situation, evidence of supply, crowd situations, or chronic drug addiction)</p>	<p>Participation in an educational session, either face-to-face or online, led by trained NHS drug education facilitators</p> <p>Aims to educate participants about health impacts, social harms and legal implications of using or possessing illegal drugs</p> <p>On completion NFA issued</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>No data</p>	<p>23% reoffended- with 45% of these committing drugs offences post-DEP, and 55% committing non-drug offences</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Drug Education Programme (DEP), Avon & Somerset, 2016-2023^{viii}</p>	<p>Deferred CC & DP</p>	<p>Be willing to participate</p> <p>Offence is eligible for an OOCDC</p> <p>Must consent to the scheme</p>	<p>Based on Durham's Checkpoint, but two options: original deferred charge, and deferral of CC</p> <p>Higher 'intensity' conditions on the deferred charge pathway</p> <p>NFA on contract completion</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>82% Deferred caution</p> <p>90-95% Deferred charge</p>	<p>Of graduates 3% reoffending rate within a year</p>	<p>No info</p>
<p>Pathfinder, Devon & Cornwall, June 2017-now^{ix}</p>							

<p>Drugs Diversion Pilot (DDP), Thames Valley Police, Dec 2018- Sept 2019^x</p>	<p>CR</p> <p>All individuals found in possession of a controlled drug under s.5 MDA (76% possession of cannabis). But must have no element of supply present, no other offences having been committed prior or alongside, no 'necessity criteria' present for arrest and whose identity the police are able to establish</p>	<p>Referral to drug service provider Cranstoun for three drug education sessions</p> <p>On refusal to engage, the suspect would be processed by other criminal justice mechanisms</p>	<p>No data</p> <p>42% completed the programme</p> <p>55% refused to engage</p>	<p>8.7% reoffending rate</p>	<p>Can reattend the scheme as many times as needed</p> <p>But cannot reattend if they refuse their first offer</p>
<p>Divert (DivertC), Cleveland, Jan 2019- now^{xi}</p>	<p>DP</p> <p>First time and 'low-level' offenders</p> <p>Referral at point of arrest</p>	<p>Following other DP schemes, with the addition of compulsory attendance of a victim awareness course</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>85% (pre-pandemic)</p>	<p>5.85% reoffending rate</p>	<p>No data</p>
<p>DIVERT (DIVERTWM), West Midlands and Mercia, Oct 2020-now^{xii}</p>	<p>CR</p> <p>Discretion of officer, yet supervising officer is to check whether scheme has been offered following arrest/ at custody</p> <p>Issued as alternate to arrest for possession of all controlled drugs</p> <p>Officer submits crime report, this is passed to the Crime Service Team who check the case criteria, and confirm CR issue</p> <p>Considered a 'light touch' intervention: no limit on previous convictions but offenders assessed as having ongoing problems with Class As which fuel acquisitive offending may not be considered</p> <p>Must consent to attend assessment</p>	<p>1-to-1 assessment where they are allocated:</p> <p>A 1-to 1 telephone session appointment with Cranstoun drug service staff (compulsory if caught with Class As), or, a 2-hour group session.</p> <p>Also refers to further services: housing, Citizens Advice, mental health needs, further drug services</p>	<p>Yes- cannot be used to evidence offence in court</p> <p>71% of referrals result in an intervention (only data)</p>	<p>11% re-arrested for drug offences in the following six months</p> <p>6.3% repeat referrals</p>	<p>Only able to be offered again if they are compliant, otherwise no limit</p>

- ¹ 'Druglink Annual Report 2022/23' ([Druglink](#), 2023).
- ² Home Office, 'Project ADDER Programme Data' ([GOV.UK](#), 15 March 2024) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/project-adder-programme-data/project-adder-programme-data>> accessed 6 April 2024.
- ³ 'Brighter Tomorrows' PEEL 2023–25: Police Effectiveness, Efficiency and Legitimacy – An Inspection of Cambridgeshire Constabulary' (HMICFRS 2024). Page 29; Charlotte Pritchard, Caroline Elywood and Jaskirat Mann, 'Project SHE (Support, Help, and Engagement)' ([Centre for Justice Innovation](#), 2022) <<https://justiceinnovation.org/project/project-she-support-help-and-engagement>> accessed 21 May 2024; 'Footprints Women's Diversionary Scheme' ([Centre for Justice Innovation](#), 2020) <<https://www.justiceinnovation.org/project/footprints-womens-diversionary-scheme-0>> accessed 21 May 2024.
- ⁴ Barni Jolão, 'Learning from Chance to Change Deferred Prosecution Pilot' (*Transition 2 Adulthood*, 19 October 2023); Rachel Kinsella, Patrick Williams and Kevin Wong, 'Chance to Change: Pilot Qualitative Research Study' (Manchester Metropolitan University; Barrow Cadbury Trust 2023).
- ⁵ Peter Neyroud and Molly Slothower, 'Operation Turning Point: interim report on a randomised trial in Birmingham, UK' (University of Cambridge, University of Maryland 2013); Garry Forsyth, 'Turning Point Project' (West Midlands Police and Crime Commissioner 2014); Peter Neyroud and Molly Slothower, 'Wielding the Sword of Damocles: The Challenges and Opportunities in Reforming Police Out-of-Court Disposals in England and Wales', in Martin Wasik and Sotirios Sapatoglou (eds), *The Management of Change in Criminal Justice: Who Knows Best?* (Palgrave Macmillan UK 2015); Peter Neyroud, 'Learning to Field Test in Policing: Using an Analysis of Completed Randomised Controlled Trials Involving the Police to Develop a Grounded Theory on the Factors Contributing to High Levels of Treatment Integrity in Police Field Experiments.' (University of Cambridge 2017); Interview with Peter Neyroud.
- ⁶ 'Expert Voice: Peter Neyroud, Former Police Officer and Lecturer in Evidenced Based Policing' (7 September 2021) <<https://justiceinnovation.org/articles/expert-voice-peter-neyroud-former-police-officer-and-lecturer-evidenced-based-policing>> accessed 7 May 2024.
- ⁷ Kevin Weir, Gillian Routledge and Stephanie Kilili, 'Checkpoint: An Innovative Programme to Navigate People Away from the Cycle of Reoffending: Implementation Phase Evaluation' (2021) 15 Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice 508; Kevin Weir and others, 'Checkpoint: An innovative Programme to navigate people away from the cycle of reoffending – A randomised control trial evaluation' (2022) 95 The Police Journal 562; Michael Fatima, 'Checkpoint' ([Centre for Justice Innovation](#), 2021) <<https://www.justiceinnovation.org/project/checkpoint>> accessed 7 April 2024; Sally Dray, 'The Checkpoint Programme QSD' (HL Library 2020).
- ⁸ Laura Parrott, 'Checkpoint Plus' ([Centre for Justice Innovation](#), 2020) <<https://www.justiceinnovation.org/project/checkpoint-plus>> accessed 6 May 2024; 'In Conversation: How the Surrey Checkpoint Programme Has Helped Tackle the Reoffending Cycle • Government Events' ([Government Events](#), 1 June 2022) <<https://www.governmentevents.co.uk/in-conversation-how-the-surrey-checkpoint-programme-has-helped-to-tackle-the-reoffending-cycle>> accessed 6 May 2024; 'Surrey Community Remedy Document' (Surrey Police and Crime Commissioner 2023); 'HMICFRS PEEL Report Findings' ([Surrey Police](#), 6 December 2023).
- ⁹ Nick de Viggiani, 'Drug Education as Diversion: A mixed methods evaluation of the Avon & Somerset Drug Education Programme' (University of the West of England; Avon & Somerset Constabulary 2022); 'Supporting young people to move away from drugs and crime in Bristol' *Avon and Somerset Police* (18 May 2022) <<https://www.avonandsomerset.police.uk/news/2022/05/supporting-young-people-to-move-away-from-drugs-and-crime-in-bristol/>> accessed 7 December 2023; 'The Drug Education Programme (DEP)' ([Bristol Drugs Project](#), 5 May 2020) <<https://www.bdp.org.uk/the-drop/the-drug-education-programme-dep/>> accessed 14 April 2024; Charlotte Pritchard, Caroline Elywood and Jaskirat Mann, 'The Drugs Education Programme (DEP)' ([Centre for Justice Innovation](#), 2022) <<https://www.justiceinnovation.org/project/drugs-education-programme-dep>> accessed 6 May 2024.
- ¹⁰ Dr Karen Goodall and others, 'A Mixed Methods Exploration of Participant Views of the Pathfinder Deferred Caution and Deferred Charge Scheme' (University of Edinburgh); 'Out of Court Resolutions (Pathfinder)' ([Devon & Cornwall Police](#)) <<https://www.devon-cornwall.police.uk/police-forces/devon-cornwall-police/areas/about-us/local-support-and-guidance/out-court-resolutions/>> accessed 6 May 2024; Isabella Anderson, 'Pathfinder' ([Centre for Justice Innovation](#), 2022) <<https://www.justiceinnovation.org/project/pathfinder>> accessed 6 May 2024.
- ¹¹ Wojciech Szyt, Lee Barnham and Jason Kew, 'Thames Valley Police Journal: Diversion - Going Soft on Drugs?' *Policing Insight* (10 December 2019) <<https://policinginsight.com/feature/analysis/thames-valley-police-journal-diversion-going-soft-on-drugs/>> accessed 14 April 2024; Robert France and Katy Barrow-Grint (eds), *Thames Valley Police Journal*, vol 4 (2019); Lee Barnham, Wojciech Szyt and Jason Kew, 'Written Evidence by Thames Valley Police DRP0073' <<https://committees.parliament.uk/writtenevidence/103655/html/>> accessed 14 April 2024; Chloe Livadaas, 'Thames Valley Roll-out Drug Diversion Scheme after Successful Pilot' *Police Oracle* (17 October 2020) <https://www.policoracle.com/news/thames-valley-roll-out-drug-diversion-scheme-after-successful-pilot_105939.html> accessed 7 December 2023; Chloe Livadaas, 'West Midlands drugs diversion scheme helps over 400 in six months' *Police Oracle* (16 June 2021) <https://www.policoracle.com/news/investigation/2021/Jun/16/west-midlands-drugs-diversion-scheme-helps-over-400-in-six-months_107394.html> accessed 7 December 2023; Lauren Bennett and Elsa Corry-Roake, 'Evidence Review: Diverting Young Adults Away from the Cycle of Crisis and Crime' (Revolving Doors Agency, New Generation Policing 2021).
- ¹² 'Divert Custody Scheme' ([Cleveland Police and Crime Commissioner](#), September 2023) <<https://www.cleveland.pcc.police.uk/working-for-you/preventing-offending/divert-custody-scheme/>> accessed 6 May 2024; Sarah Gibbons, 'Divert Programme Delivers Significant Reduction in Reoffending by Addressing Underlying Needs' (*Policing Insight*, 23 September 2021)

<<https://policingsight.com/feature/divert-programme-delivers-significant-reduction-in-reoffending-by-addressing-underlying-needs/>> accessed 6 May 2024; Maysa Clam and Isabella Anderson, 'Cleveland Divert' (*Centre for Justice Innovation*, 2022) <<https://www.justiceinnovation.org/project/cleveland-divert/>> accessed 6 May 2024.

⁵¹ Nadine Hendrie and others, 'The West Midlands Police Drug Diversion Scheme DIVERT: Descriptive Manual' (Canterbury: University of Kent 2023); Susan Goddard, 'Drug Divert Programme Cranstoun (1370A/22)' (*Freedom of Information - West Midlands Police*, 31 October 2022) <<https://foi.west-midlands.police.uk/drug-divert-programme-cranstoun-1370a-22/>> accessed 7 December 2023; 'Drug Diversion Following Stop and Search and Custody: The "Divert" Programme' (*College of Policing*, 10 January 2024) <<https://www.college.police.uk/support-forces/practices/drug-diversion-following-stop-and-search-and-custody-divert-programme>> accessed 14 April 2024; Jason Watt, 'DIVERT' (*Centre for Justice Innovation*, 2021) <<https://justiceinnovation.org/project/divert/>> accessed 14 April 2024.

Appendix B

Abbreviation Meaning

<i>ACMD</i>	Advisory Council on the Misuse of Drugs
<i>BAME</i>	Black, Asian, or Minority Ethnic
<i>C2C</i>	Chance to Change Pilot
<i>CC</i>	Conditional Caution
<i>CCP</i>	Community Cautions
<i>CJS</i>	Criminal Justice System
<i>CoP</i>	Code of practice
<i>CPS</i>	Crown Prosecution Service
<i>CR</i>	Community Resolution
<i>CW</i>	Cannabis Warning
<i>CP</i>	Deferred Prosecution
<i>DC</i>	Diversiory Cautions
<i>DDP</i>	Drugs Diversion Pilot
<i>DEP</i>	Drugs Education Pilot
<i>E&W</i>	England and Wales
<i>FCT</i>	Full-Code Test

<i>FPN</i>	Fixed-Penalty Notices
<i>KW</i>	Khat Warning
<i>NEET</i>	Not in Education, Employment, or Training
<i>NFA</i>	No Further Action
<i>NPS</i>	Novel Psychoactive Substance
<i>MoJ</i>	Ministry of Justice
<i>NPCC</i>	National Police Chiefs Council
<i>OOCD</i>	Out-of-Court Disposal
<i>PNC</i>	Police National Computer
<i>PND</i>	Penalty Notice for Disorder
<i>PTSD</i>	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder
<i>RCT</i>	Randomised Controlled Trials
<i>RJ</i>	Restorative Justice
<i>S&S</i>	Stop and Search
<i>SC</i>	Simple Caution
<i>TP</i>	Turning Point study
<i>TTPF</i>	Two-Tier Plus Framework under the PSCSA
<i>UN</i>	United Nations

Appendix C

Table on use and enforcement of Community Resolutions, Community Cautions, Diversionary Cautions, from the Draft Code of Practice on Diversionary and Community Cautions, (Ministry of Justice, 2024) page 13. see bibliography.

	Community Resolution	Community Caution	Diversionary Caution
Use	No statutory restrictions on use. Use is in line with National Police Chiefs Council policy and guidance.	Can be used for any offence – other than an excluded offence. (Excluded offences are indictable-only and either way or summary only offences as prescribed in regulations – see Part 5).	Can be used for any offence. In the case of indictable only offences – only in exceptional circumstances <i>and</i> with consent of the Director of Public Prosecutions.
Enforcement	Non-compliance with a Community Resolution is not enforceable. No power of arrest or detention following non-compliance.	Non-compliance cannot be prosecuted. Authorised user can rescind the condition and attach a financial penalty (if this was not originally a condition). If this penalty remains unpaid, it can be registered for enforcement as a court fine. No power of arrest or detention following non-compliance.	Non-compliance with conditions can result in the offender being prosecuted for the original offence. Power of arrest and detention following non-compliance.